

Co-funded by
the European Union

Europe's Civic University Alliance

CIVIS Blended Intensive Programmes 2024-2025: quality, impact, and strategic development

An evidence-based evaluation of learning, mobility, administration,
and institutional integration

January 2026

civis.eu

Member universities :

Associate member universities :

The CIVIS Universities

Here are the names of the universities and their acronyms as we use them in CIVIS.

AMU	Aix-Marseille université
NKUA	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
UB	University of Bucharest
ULB	Université libre de Bruxelles
UofG	University of Glasgow
UNIL	University of Lausanne
UAM	Universidad Autónoma de Madrid
SUR	Sapienza Università di Roma
PLUS	Paris Lodron University of Salzburg
SU	Stockholm University
UT	Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen

CIVIS – Europe's Civic University Alliance

CIVIS is a European Civic University formed by the alliance of 11 leading research higher education institutions across Europe: Aix-Marseille Université, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Université libre de Bruxelles, University of Bucharest, University of Glasgow, University of Lausanne, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Sapienza Università di Roma, Paris Lodron University of Salzburg, Stockholm University and Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen.

It brings together a community of more than 470,000 students and 58,000 staff members including 35,000 academics and researchers.

The Authors

Mihaela STÎNGU, Education Unit
Alexandru CARȚIȘ, Head of Education Unit
Simona IFTIMESCU, Work Package 8
Anna-Karin BJÖRLING, Quality Officer
Evelina SKÖLD, Educational Quality Officer
and the entire **CIVIS Community**

1 Alliance
11 Universities
Countless Possibilities

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive Summary	6
1. Overall surveys statistics	8
2. Demographic and participation profile	10
2.1. Home universities	11
2.2. Education level of students	11
2.3. Distribution of responses by BIPs	12
2.4. Previous CIVIS experience of students	14
2.5. Participation patterns and engagement levels	14
3. Administrative aspects	16
3.1. Application process	17
3.2. ECTS recognition	19
3.3. BIP validation process	22
3.4. Support received by students and coordinators	24
4. Mobility experience	29
4.1. Administrative and organisational aspects of the mobility process	30
4.2. Green mobility	32
4.3. Satisfaction with key aspects of the physical mobility	33
5. Teaching and learning experience	36
5.1. Implementation of teaching and learning activities	37
5.2. Quality and relevance of teaching and learning activities	38
5.3. Active learning and student participation	41
5.4. Assessment and learning outcomes	42
6. Digital learning environment and support	47
6.1. Use of the Digital Campus	48
6.2. Quality of digital tools and environments	49
7. CIVIS educational values and interdisciplinarity	52
7.1. Reflection of CIVIS values in the programmes	53
7.2. Challenge-based education and impact on engagement	54
7.3. Interdisciplinarity	56
8. Communication, outreach and future engagement	59
9. Best practices and added value	62
9.1. Best practices	63
9.2. Added value	64
10. Challenges and areas for improvement	66

10.1. Challenges	67
10.2. Improvements	68
11. Conclusions and recommendations	70
Annexes	73
Annex I. Programme coordinators survey 2025	74
Annex II. Student survey 2025	80

Citation

Stîngu, M., Carțiș, A., Iftimescu, S., Björling, A.-K., Sköld, E., & CIVIS – Europe's Civic University Alliance. (2026). *CIVIS Blended Intensive Programmes 2024-2025: quality, impact, and strategic development*. CIVIS – Europe's Civic University Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18504165>

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents a comprehensive evaluation of the **CIVIS Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs)** implemented during the **2024-2025 academic year**. Its purpose is to assess the quality, effectiveness, and added value of BIPs from both student and coordinator perspectives, with a particular focus on **administrative processes, mobility arrangements, teaching and learning experiences, digital environments, and the integration of CIVIS educational values**. The report aims to inform strategic decision-making, quality enhancement, and the future development of BIPs within the CIVIS Alliance.

The analysis draws on quantitative and qualitative data collected through structured online surveys administered to both students and coordinators. A total of **611 students** (out of **1.534 students, 39.83%**) who participated in CIVIS BIPs responded to the student survey, representing a wide range of disciplines, institutions, and levels of study (bachelor, master, and doctoral levels). In parallel, **40 responses from BIP coordinators** were collected, representing **39 BIPs out of the 70** implemented during the reference academic year, with one response consolidating input from two coordinators. Together, these data provide a robust and multi-perspective evidence base for assessing programme performance and impact.

Overall, the findings indicate a high level of satisfaction and maturity in the implementation of CIVIS BIPs.

From an **administrative perspective**, students and coordinators largely perceive application, validation, and organisational processes as accessible and well structured. **Administrative support emerges as one of the strongest pillars of the CIVIS BIP ecosystem**, playing a key role in enabling participation and mitigating procedural complexity. Nonetheless, challenges persist in relation to **documentation requirements, Learning Agreement procedures, and uneven ECTS recognition** across institutions.

Regarding **mobility**, students report very positive experiences with the **organisation and completion of physical mobility**, as well as with **course locations and accessibility**. Financial and informational aspects remain the main pressure points, particularly the timing of payments and clarity regarding funding conditions. Uptake of **green mobility** remains limited, not due to lack of motivation, but because of structural constraints related to time, cost, geography, and administrative feasibility.

The **teaching and learning experience** constitutes one of the strongest dimensions of CIVIS BIPs. Students report very high satisfaction with the quality and relevance of learning activities, especially those that are experiential, practice-based, and interactive, such as workshops, fieldwork, laboratory activities, and group projects. A strong alignment between announced programme design and actual delivery reinforces trust and credibility. Active learning, international collaboration, and interdisciplinarity are consistently highlighted as key strengths.

Regarding **digital platforms**, tools such as Moodle and institutional systems are generally perceived as reliable and supportive for blended learning. However, the CIVIS mobility platform is frequently described by coordinators as complex and time-consuming, particularly for managing student status and post-mobility processes.

Finally, the analysis confirms the **strong added value of CIVIS BIPs**, particularly in terms of international exposure, interdisciplinary learning, skills development, and network building. CIVIS values – *such as civic engagement, challenge-based learning, and collaboration across disciplines and institutions* – are clearly reflected in programme design and participant experiences.

Key challenges identified across the report include **administrative complexity, inconsistent ECTS recognition, time and workload constraints, uneven availability of pedagogical support, operational difficulties related to green mobility**, and the **usability of digital platforms**. These challenges are largely systemic and linked to institutional, regulatory, and infrastructural conditions rather than to programme quality itself.

Based on these findings, the report recommends further **harmonisation and simplification of administrative and recognition procedures, earlier and clearer communication regarding mobility funding and green travel options, targeted improvements to digital platforms, and stronger institutional support for pedagogical design and interdisciplinary innovation**. Strengthening the recognition of academic coordination work and systematically sharing best practices across the CIVIS Alliance are also identified as key levers for enhancing sustainability and impact.

Overall, the report concludes that **CIVIS BIPs represent a high-quality, high-impact educational format**, well aligned with the strategic objectives of the CIVIS Alliance. Addressing the remaining structural and operational challenges will further strengthen their inclusiveness, effectiveness, and long-term contribution to European university cooperation.

1

OVERALL SURVEYS STATISTICS

A total of **70 Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs)** implemented during the **2024-2025 academic year** were referenced in this analysis.

The survey addressed to **CIVIS BIP coordinators** was a **post-implementation follow-up questionnaire** designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative feedback on programme design, delivery, and impact. It consisted of **nine thematic sections** and included a combination of **closed-ended questions (multiple choice, yes/no, rating scales)** and **open-ended questions** allowing for detailed reflections.

The **BIP coordinator survey** covered:

- (I) *background information on the academic team and programme;*
- (II) *student participation and completion data;*
- (III) *types of support received (financial, administrative, technical, dissemination, pedagogical, and other), including satisfaction levels;*
- (IV) *accreditation and validation issues;*
- (V) *teaching and learning activities and active student participation;*
- (VI) *assessment formats and learning outcomes;*
- (VII) *innovative pedagogies and reflection of CIVIS values, including interdisciplinarity;*
- (VIII) *use of the CIVIS Digital Campus and shared digital tools;*
- (IX) *best practices, added value, challenges, and areas for improvement.*

From 70 BIP coordinators, **39 BIPS were represented**, with one BIP summarising responses from two coordinators, leading up to **40 responses from BIP coordinators**.

The **student survey** was a **post-implementation online questionnaire** designed to capture students' experiences of participating in CIVIS BIPs and Micro-Programmes during the 2024–2025 academic year. It combined **closed-ended questions (multiple choice, Likert-type scales, and satisfaction ratings)** with **open-ended questions** allowing students to provide qualitative feedback and suggestions.

The **student survey** was structured into five main thematic sections. These covered:

- (I) *academic and background information (home university, level of study, previous CIVIS experience, and programme attended);*
- (II) *administrative aspects, including the application process, challenges encountered, and satisfaction with institutional support;*
- (III) *mobility experience for programmes involving physical mobility, with a focus on organisation, funding, green travel, and satisfaction with mobility-related services;*
- (IV) *learning experience, addressing the quality and relevance of teaching and learning activities, assessment methods, alignment between announced and actual activities, interdisciplinary and challenge-based learning, reflection of CIVIS values, and digital learning environments;*
- (V) *recognition and follow-up aspects, including ECTS recognition, dissemination channels, intention to participate in future CIVIS activities, and additional open comments.*

Out of **1.534 students** which participated in the CIVIS BIPs implemented during the 2024-2025 academic year, **611 students (39.83%)** successfully responded to the feedback survey, as part of the overall follow-up of the **CIVIS educational portfolio**, coordinated by the CIVIS Education Unit in cooperation with the CIVIS Quality Officer.

2

DEMOGRAPHIC AND PARTICIPATION PROFILE

2.1. Home universities

Figure 1. Number of respondents (students and coordinators) per home university

As **Figure 1** shows, the distribution of responses from **coordinators** reflects the percentage of BIPs organised by each university, with the highest shares coming from **NKUA (22.50%)**, **UB (20.00%)**, and **SUR (17.50%)**. **All CIVIS European universities** and **4 of the 6 CIVIS associate member universities in Africa** are represented in the **students'** survey.

2.2. Education level of students

Figure 2 shows a **predominantly postgraduate audience**, with **master's students** forming the largest group (**n = 288, 47.14%**), followed by **bachelor's students (n = 207, 33.88%)**, while **doctoral students** account for a smaller but still meaningful share (**n = 116, 18.99%**), indicating strong engagement beyond the undergraduate level.

Figure 2. Students' education level

2.3. Distribution of responses by BIPs

Table 1 presents the full list of CIVIS BIPs included in the dataset, together with the corresponding number of respondents for each activity and each category (students/coordinators)

Table 1. Name of BIP attended/coordinated

Answer	Students		Coordinators	
	Count	%	Count	%
À l'école des Anciens. War and its representations from the perspective of ancient rhetoric'	3	0.49%	0	0.00%
A revival of ideologies? Ideas and opinions in contemporary democracies	1	0.16%	0	0.00%
AI and STEAM: Changing Learning, Shaping Futures	11	1.80%	1	2.50%
Anatomy of trauma and its implications for addictions	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
Animal sacrifice and its critics between past and present	11	1.80%	1	2.50%
Attractiveness, branding and governance of regions	4	0.65%	1	2.50%
Basic Cell Biology	11	1.80%	1	2.50%
Basis and methods of localisation. Translation of computer products and video games	4	0.65%	1	2.50%
Biological Basis of Aging and Related Diseases	12	1.96%	0	0.00%
Brulau: Ecole doctorale francophone en études de genre	8	1.31%	0	0.00%
Civic Engagement & Football: A Transdisciplinary Approach	9	1.47%	1	2.50%
Climate change and landscape evolution in the Mediterranean context	10	1.64%	0	0.00%
Climate change imprint on a tectonically active landscape	10	1.64%	1	2.50%
Co-creating urban futures	10	1.64%	1	2.50%
Communicating Social Science and Humanities: Mastering Methodological Challenges and Early Publishing	11	1.80%	1	2.50%
Delve into Santorini's geological marvels and volcanic risks	3	0.49%	1	2.50%
Democracy, citizens and new forms of civic engagement	4	0.65%	0	0.00%
Diachronic Linguistics in the 21st century	9	1.47%	0	0.00%
Environmental challenges facing Danube River Basin	11	1.80%	2	5.00%
EU Decision making and its institutions: discover the heart of Brussels	14	2.29%	0	0.00%
Euro-African Trade and Investment Relations and the Polycrisis	12	1.96%	1	2.50%

Europe and the rule of law	22	3.60%	0	0.00%
European Election in times of (poli)crises.	2	0.33%	0	0.00%
European Renaissance IV: Western versus Eastern Europe	7	1.15%	1	2.50%
Experimental Models in Molecular Biomedicine (EMMB)	11	1.80%	1	2.50%
Exploring Language Varieties in the Diaspora: Methodological and Theoretical Approaches	6	0.98%	0	0.00%
H2O Pollution: holistic approach and nature based solutions	0	0.00%	0	0.00%
How to write a paper and talk about science	9	1.47%	1	2.50%
Humanities within Medicine and Health	15	2.45%	0	0.00%
Immuno-oncology in the spatial omics era	7	1.15%	0	0.00%
Interplay of Landscape, Tectonics and Climate Change in the Mediterranean context'	3	0.49%	0	0.00%
Law, Community and Justice	3	0.49%	0	0.00%
Let's prove it! Reasoning in different contexts	4	0.65%	0	0.00%
Linguistic cultures and communities in Europe (past and present). Building the EUROTALES museum.	8	1.31%	0	0.00%
Maternal and neonatal vaccination	7	1.15%	1	2.50%
Medical Matters in Post/colonial Situations/ Matérialités médicales en situations post/coloniales	4	0.65%	0	0.00%
Mental Health, Sport & Physical Activity (MHSPA)	8	1.31%	0	0.00%
Molecular Scale Biophysics	18	2.95%	1	2.50%
Multicultural and multilingual Mediation (German language)	12	1.96%	1	2.50%
Natural products: applications, formulations	4	0.65%	0	0.00%
Navigating Uncertainty: Building Sustainable Skills for Life	9	1.47%	0	0.00%
Neurobiology of Mental Disorders	12	1.96%	1	2.50%
New insight in Drug design and discovery: from the bench to the patient	16	2.62%	1	2.50%
Non-coding RNAs in Health and Disease	7	1.15%	1	2.50%
Novel Research and Ethics: from Neuroscience to AI	2	0.33%	0	0.00%
Online fake news and disinformation: recognize and verify	4	0.65%	1	2.50%
Participatory tools for urban nature planning and management	9	1.47%	1	2.50%
Pluralism of economic ideas	2	0.33%	0	0.00%
PostRacial Transmodernities: Afro-European Relations, Mediterranean Trajectories & Intercultural Reciprocities	8	1.31%	1	2.50%
Quantifying vulnerability to natural hazards in changing climate patterns. New perspectives and methods	4	0.65%	0	0.00%
Quantifying vulnerability to natural hazards in changing climate patterns. New perspectives and methods	1	0.16%	1	2.50%
Radiotheranostics in Nuclear Medicine	12	1.96%	1	2.50%
Rare Diseases at the Omics era: Current tools for frequent challenges	16	2.62%	0	0.00%
Reading Between the Humorous Lines	6	0.98%	1	2.50%
Refugees, Migrants, and Exiles in German and Comparative Literature	9	1.47%	0	0.00%
Religion and power in the Eastern Mediterranean	13	2.13%	1	2.50%
Rights and Democracy. The Multilevel Protection of Fundamental Rights and the Role of Constitutional and European Courts	17	2.78%	1	2.50%
Roman Mobilities and their Afterlives	9	1.47%	0	0.00%
Rome CIVIS Orchestra Academy 2025	26	4.26%	1	2.50%
Science, Ethics & Governance of Human Genome Editing	7	1.15%	1	2.50%
Scientific Communication and Linguistic Corpora: Tools for Interdisciplinary Research	7	1.15%	1	2.50%
Social Sciences Going Public - Research and Practice with, in and for the Society	28	4.58%	1	2.50%
Strategic Communication for Social Change	3	0.49%	0	0.00%

Surgical Anatomy- from theory to dissection	8	1.31%	1	2.50%
Teaching and Studying Turkish Politics through Literature (second edition, 2025)	8	1.31%	1	2.50%
The challenge of sustainability in European democracies	2	0.33%	0	0.00%
The Ethics of narratives: between old and new media	9	1.47%	0	0.00%
The Heritage of Money and Coinage: objects and practices in transformation	21	3.44%	0	0.00%
TRANSMOUNT - Transitions in Mountain Environments	1	0.16%	0	0.00%
Understanding Earth	11	1.80%	1	2.50%
Using Drones in Environmental Sciences	6	0.98%	1	2.50%
Total	611	100%	40	100%

2.4. Previous CIVIS experience of students

Among the 611 students who completed the feedback survey, **77.74%** indicated that they had participated in previous CIVIS activities, while the remaining **22.26%** experienced CIVIS for the first time through this BIP. This proportion confirms the capacity of the CIVIS Alliance to attract both new learners and a stable cohort of returning participants who continue to engage in the diverse learning opportunities offered across partner universities. Students have previously engaged mainly in **CIVIS BIPs**, complemented by **CIVIS Summer Schools**, **MOOCs**, **exchange semesters**, and **thematic courses**, covering a wide range of disciplines from life sciences and public health to social sciences, humanities, and environmental studies.

The most frequently mentioned programmes include BIPs such as *Democratic Memories in Global Perspective*, *Technical Innovations: Applications to Immuno-Oncology*, *Rights and Democracy*, *Environmental Challenges Facing the Danube River*, and *Drug Design and Discovery*, illustrating a strong emphasis on interdisciplinary, international, and challenge-based learning within the CIVIS alliance.

2.5. Participation patterns and engagement levels

Across the BIPs included in this report, a total of **1,833 students were enrolled**. Of these, as **Figure 2** shows, **1,455 students successfully passed their programmes**, corresponding to **79.38% of all enrolled students**. A further **265 students (14.46%) were enrolled but did not show up**, meaning that they were admitted and received confirmation but did not ultimately participate in any programme activities. In addition, **113 students (6.16%) participated in at least part of the programme but did not pass**, either due to withdrawal during implementation or failure to meet assessment requirements.

Figure 2. Distribution of student participation and completion outcomes across CIVIS BIPs

When focusing only on students who **effectively participated in programme activities** (i.e. excluding no-shows), **completion rates are particularly high**. Out of 1,568 participating students, **92.79% successfully completed their programmes**, while **7.21% did not pass**. This indicates that attrition occurs predominantly before programme start, rather than during implementation.

On average, per programme, this corresponds to approximately **47 enrolled students**, of whom **37 passed**, **7 did not show up**, and **3 participated but did not pass**. These figures underline the overall robustness of programme delivery and student engagement once participation is initiated, while also pointing to the pre-programme phase as the main area where participation losses occur.

From an implementation perspective, the data suggest that targeted measures aimed at strengthening **confirmation, communication, and follow-up before programme start** could further reduce no-show rates and optimise cohort stability. At the same time, the very high completion rate among participating students provides strong evidence of the effectiveness and pedagogical sustainability of the CIVIS BIP model once students are actively engaged.

3

ADMINISTRATIVE ASPECTS

3.1. Application process

This subsection provides an integrated analysis of students' experiences with the **administrative dimension of the CIVIS BIPs application process**, combining their **overall perception of the application procedure (Q7)**, the **specific challenges encountered during application (Q8)**, and their **level of satisfaction with key organisational aspects of the application process (Q9)**. Taken together, these perspectives allow for a nuanced understanding of both the **accessibility** of the application process and the **operational demands** it places on students.

At an overall level, students reported a **strongly positive perception of the application process**. As illustrated in **Figure 3**, more than four out of five respondents assessed the process as **easy** or **very easy** (**80.36%**, **n = 491**). In contrast, **18.82%** (**n = 115**) perceived it as **difficult**, while only **0.86%** (**n = 5**) described it as **very difficult**. The mean score (**M = 2.890**) and the narrow 95% confidence interval [**2.847-2.925**], combined with a low standard deviation (**SD = 0.552**), indicate a high level of convergence in students' evaluations. This suggests that, across diverse institutional contexts, the application process is generally experienced as accessible and navigable.

Figure 3. Students' overall perception of the CIVIS BIP application process

However, this overall positive assessment is complemented by a more differentiated picture when examining the **specific challenges encountered during application**. As shown in **Figure 4**, students' difficulties are not primarily linked to understanding how to apply, but rather to the **administrative and procedural requirements embedded in the process**. The most frequently reported challenge was **obtaining the signature on the Learning Agreement** (**17.14%**, **n = 213**), followed closely by the perception that **too much information and documentation were required** (**16.98%**, **n = 211**). These findings point to the complexity of formal approval procedures that characterise transnational educational initiatives involving multiple institutions and regulatory frameworks.

Figure 4. Main challenges encountered during the CIVIS BIP application process

Related challenges further reinforce this interpretation. **Obtaining the relevant documents from administrative staff** was selected in **14.66% (n = 179)** of responses, highlighting the reliance on local administrative workflows that may vary significantly across institutions. In parallel, **recognition of ECTS obtained through BIPs** emerged as a concern for **10.40% (n = 127)** of respondents, indicating that questions of academic recognition already surface at the application stage and may shape students' perceptions of risk and effort. Issues related to **information clarity and timing** – such as **lack of information on the application process (9.91%, n = 121)** and **too little time for application (7.45%, n = 91)** – were present but less prominent, suggesting that information is generally available, even if administratively demanding to act upon.

Importantly, nearly **one in five responses indicated that no challenges were encountered (17.85%, n = 221)**, confirming that for a substantial group of students the application process functions smoothly. At the same time, the relatively wide dispersion of responses (**M = 4.428; SD = 2.130; SE = 0.061; 95% CI [4.308-4.547]**) reflects the heterogeneity of administrative environments across the CIVIS Alliance and underscores that students' experiences are shaped not only by central programme design, but also by local institutional practices.

Students' evaluations of the **organisational aspects of the application process itself (Q9)** provide an important complementary perspective. Despite the procedural challenges identified above, students expressed **consistently high levels of satisfaction** with the **schedule, overall organisation, and digital platforms** used during the application phase, as shown by **Figure 5**. This suggests that administrative complexity does not necessarily translate into perceptions of disorganisation or inefficiency.

Figure 5. Students' satisfaction with organisational aspects of the CIVIS BIP application process

Satisfaction with the **application schedule** was particularly strong, with **87.40%** of respondents indicating that they were **rather satisfied (43.21%, n = 264)** or **very satisfied (44.19%, n = 270)**. The mean score ($M = 3.277$, 95% CI [3.215-3.339]) and moderate variability ($SD = 0.781$) indicate that, for most students, the sequencing and timing of application-related steps were perceived as appropriate, even when documentation requirements were demanding.

A similarly positive pattern was observed for the **overall organisation of the application process**, which received the highest proportion of **very satisfied (46.81%, n = 286)**. Together with those who were **rather satisfied (38.79%, n = 237)**, this results in **over 85% positive evaluations**, supported by a mean score of 3.273 (95% CI [3.207-3.339]). These findings suggest that students distinguish between **administrative workload** and **organisational coherence**, perceiving the process as well-structured even when it requires substantial effort.

Satisfaction with the **digital platforms used during the application process** was likewise **high**, with **86.41%** of respondents reporting positive evaluations and a mean score of 3.260 (95% CI [3.198-3.322]). The relatively low standard deviation ($SD = 0.785$) indicates that digital tools generally supported students' engagement with the application procedures, playing a stabilising role within a complex administrative environment.

Taken together, the findings from Q7, Q8, and Q9 reveal a **layered administrative experience**. Students largely perceive the application process as **accessible, well-organised, and digitally functional**, while simultaneously identifying **specific procedural bottlenecks** related to documentation, approvals, and academic recognition. This pattern suggests that the CIVIS application framework has reached a level of **operational maturity**, but that further gains could be achieved by simplifying or better synchronising formal requirements across institutions.

From an implementation perspective, these results point to clear opportunities for enhancement, particularly in relation to **streamlining documentation workflows, clarifying Learning Agreement procedures, and strengthening early communication around ECTS recognition**. Addressing these areas may help reduce perceived administrative burden while preserving the organisational strengths that students already recognise, thereby contributing to a more seamless and confidence-building entry point into CIVIS BIPs.

3.2. ECTS recognition

The responses regarding the **curricular embedding of BIPs** reveal differing degrees of integration across universities. While some BIPs were formally incorporated into existing programmes, others were not, and the analysis examines the reasons behind this lack of embedding. Participants pointed to factors such as **institutional procedures, timing and administrative constraints, limited recognition mechanisms, or misalignment with existing curricular structures**. These explanations offer insight into the systemic and organisational conditions that shape the integration of BIPs within university curricula.

Analysis of the **coordinators' feedback** shows that only **45% of coordinators** mentioned **the integration of BIPs in the university's curriculum**. Coordinators mentioned a range of structural, administrative and curricular barriers that prevented the formal embedding BIPs into their study programmes. The resulting mean score ($M = 1.55$, 95% CI [1.394-1.706]), together with a moderate standard deviation ($SD = 0.504$) and a low standard error ($SE = 0.080$), indicates a relatively consistent pattern of responses among participants.

A major reason was the **absence of an institutional framework to recognise BIPs within existing degrees**. Some coordinators explicitly noted that *"the BIP was not embedded due to the lack of an institutional framework for recognition..."*, while others reported that administrative bodies offered *"only NO as answer"* when integration was proposed or that *"the student could not exchange courses with the BIP due to a decision of the University's central administration."* These responses point to rigid internal procedures and limited administrative openness to new mobility formats.

In other cases, coordinators struggled with **curricular or ECTS misalignment**, making it difficult to incorporate a BIP across different programmes or faculties. Coordinators highlighted that “*various ECTS systems of the partner universities*” created incompatibilities, or that “*similar programmes did not exist in all partnering faculties, making it difficult to insert the BIP in all students' curricula.*” Even when the content was relevant, some coordinators indicated that “*the content complements the curriculum, but is not included in it; credits are recognised, but added to the mandatory ones.*” Several answers noted that the BIP did not align with existing study programmes, with remarks such as “*there are no classes in communication of science to non-trained publics*” and some BIPs were part of entirely new initiatives that “*did not fit in an existing university programme.*”

Several coordinators indicated that the BIP was **too new or not sufficiently developed for integration**. Examples include statements such as “*the process of integrating CIVIS BIP courses into our university's curriculum has not begun yet,*” or simply “*we did not have time to include it in the curriculum.*” In such cases, integration was perceived as a long-term objective rather than an immediate possibility.

For many universities, the BIP was intentionally positioned as an **additional or optional activity** rather than part of the formal curriculum. Respondents noted that “*the BIP is included for our students as additional activities, and they get a complementary document describing the ECTS,*” or that it was “*included as an optional activity (not a course) for extra credits.*” Even where relevance was recognised, the programme remained outside the official curriculum structures.

In some cases, **national or institutional regulations** posed limitations. For example, one institution explained that “*Romanian legislation... does not allow students to take international courses to compensate the local curriculum,*” while another described administrative restrictions whereby students transitioning between programmes were “*not eligible*” despite their academic interest.

A few responses revealed **uncertainty about the concept of curriculum embedding**, with comments such as “*I am not sure to understand what is meant by curriculum,*” or “*I have not researched into this.*” This suggests variable levels of familiarity with the administrative pathways needed for integration.

Responses of **students** indicate that while **most students were able to have their ECTS credits recognised**, a substantial minority encountered difficulties, as **Figure 6** shows. Out of 611 respondents, **67.59% (n=413) answered 'Yes'**, confirming that they were able to recognise their ECTS, whereas **32.41% (n=198) answered 'No'**, indicating unsuccessful or unresolved recognition. Treating 'Yes' as 1 and 'No' as 2 on a two-point scale, the results yield a mean of 1.324, which is clearly closer to 'Yes' than to 'No', confirming that recognition was more common than not. The standard deviation of 0.468 and standard error of 0.019 indicate relatively limited dispersion around this mean, and the 95% confidence interval from 1.287 to 1.61 suggests that this estimate is statistically precise and robust.

Figure 6. Ability to recognise ECTS based on students' responses

From an evaluation perspective, these findings show that **ECTS recognition works for most, but not all, participants**. Roughly one in three students reporting that they could not recognise their ECTS represents a significant barrier to the full academic benefit and perceived value of participation. This points to the need for clearer procedures, stronger institutional agreements, and more systematic support to ensure that recognition of credits is consistent, timely, and predictable across all partner institutions.

Among those students whose ECTS were recognised, **Figure 7** shows that universities used a **mix of approaches**, with a slight preference for **recognition outside the core curriculum**. Specifically, **40.04% (n=179)** reported that the **credits were embedded in their degree as part of the regular ECTS**, while **43.62% (n=195)** indicated that they were **recognised as extra ECTS in the diploma supplement**. A further **16.33% (n=73)** selected 'Other', suggesting the **use of more ad hoc or institution-specific arrangements** (such as recognition as elective modules, certificates, or internal credits without formal transcript embedding).

Figure 7. Approaches on ECTS recognition at home university

When coded on a 3-point scale (1 = embedded in the degree, 2 = extra ECTS in the diploma supplement, 3 = other), these responses yield a mean of 1.763, located between options 1 and 2 but closer to 2, indicating that, on average, recognition tends to occur slightly more often via additional ECTS in the diploma supplement than as fully integrated degree credits. The standard deviation of 0.713 shows a moderate spread between the three modes, while the standard error of 0.034 and the 95% confidence interval of 1.697-1.829 indicate that this estimate is statistically precise. Overall, the data suggest that while many institutions integrate CIVIS-related learning directly into regular study programmes, a large share still relies on recognition through the diploma supplement or other mechanisms, pointing to a partially standardised but still heterogeneous landscape of ECTS recognition practices across universities.

The open-ended explanations provided by students who could not have their ECTS recognised reveal a combination of administrative, institutional, and communication-related barriers. A first major theme concerns **administrative refusal or lack of supporting procedures at the home university**. Several respondents reported that *"the university does not support the recognition"* or that *"our university does not work with ECTS,"* indicating that in some cases the institutional framework simply does not allow or has not yet implemented recognition of such credits. Related to this, **differences in institutional rules and credit systems** were frequently mentioned, particularly by students in programmes not organised around ECTS. For example, one student stated that *"my program of studies (PhD studies) does not follow an ECTS assessment system,"* while another explained that *"the recognition of the ECTS is not yet opened at my home university."* These comments point to structural incompatibilities between CIVIS offerings and certain home-institution regulations, and/or to a lack of understanding of the ECTS system among students.

A second set of issues relates to **timing and procedural delays**. Some students reported that transcripts or formal documentation arrived too late to be processed within their institutions' deadlines, as in the case of *"the transcript of records [was sent] too late for my home university to accept them"* or *"the process is not complete yet."* Others described **course mismatch or lack of formal agreements**, for instance *"the program was not eligible with the courses from my home university."* In addition to the concrete administrative and procedural reasons for non-recognition of ECTS, the responses also highlight how these problems affect students' perceptions of the value of their participation. Several comments convey disappointment or frustration when expectations about recognition were raised but not fulfilled, for example, *"The professor from home university said to as it was going to be embedded in our diploma (not as regular ECTS) but when I asked the secretary office, they replied, quite angrily I might add, that 'We don't add such things as extras on your diploma',"* suggesting gaps between what was promised and what could be formally recognised.

Finally, **communication problems and lack of clarity** also emerge as important factors. Some students indicated that they were unsure about the process itself, with one stating *"I don't know what ECTS is,"* and another reporting that *"I asked if I could equate [sic!] my ECTS at my home university, and she told me that the University [...] simply does not transfer credits."* These experiences suggest that, beyond technical incompatibilities, unclear communication and lack of transparent procedures can undermine trust in institutional support and reduce the perceived academic benefit of CIVIS activities. From a quality perspective, this underlines the importance not only of formal recognition agreements, but also of proactive information, clear expectations, and reliable follow-up so that students understand from the outset what recognition is possible and how it will be implemented.

Overall, these accounts show that non-recognition of ECTS is rarely due to the CIVIS activities themselves, but rather to administrative hurdles, incompatibilities in credit systems, delays in documentation, and insufficient information or follow-up at the institutional level.

3.3. BIP validation process

The perceptions shared among BIP coordinators about the **validation process for CIVIS BIPs (Q8, Q9)** highlight varying levels of clarity, efficiency, and institutional support across universities. The analysis explores how respondents evaluate this process, including its perceived strengths and challenges, as well as how the validation steps unfold in practice, from initial proposal and quality assurance checks to approval by academic bodies and administrative units. These insights provide a contextual understanding of the procedures adopted at both university and CIVIS levels and how these are experienced by those implementing CIVIS initiatives.

Figure 8. Coordinators' perceptions on the BIPs validation process

The distribution of responses, dominated by **easy (43.90%, n=18)** and **very easy (21.95%, n=9)**, with no participants reporting it as very difficult, suggests that the validation of CIVIS BIPs is overall perceived as accessible and manageable, although a notable proportion (**34.15%, n=14**) still experience some level of difficulty, pointing to room for further simplification and harmonisation of procedures, as **Figure 8** shows. The resulting mean score ($M = 2.878$, 95% CI [2.649–3.107]), together with a moderate standard deviation ($SD = 0.748$) and a low standard error ($SE = 0.117$), indicates a generally consistent perception of the validation process across respondents.

When asked to briefly describe how the process looked like, coordinators mentioned various aspects regarding administrative and procedural issues.

- **Administrative procedures and approval pathways.** Many coordinators describe multi-step internal approval processes involving departments, faculties, and central bodies. This includes structured pathways such as *“a course needs to be approved by the Department Board and the Faculty Education Board,”* or *“approval from the Department of Biology, then the Faculty of Sciences, followed by review by the Training and University Life Commission.”* Some universities report smooth, well-defined procedures, noting that *“the validation process is simple and clearly defined”* or *“automatic recognition of ECTS.”* Others highlight complex or lengthy processes, mentioning *“numerous steps... chasing people to sign documents,”* and *“a very long application process (18+ months).”*
- **Administrative support, communication, and institutional collaboration.** Several coordinators emphasised the importance of supportive staff structures. They praised local efforts, stating: *“The CIVIS Coordinators have done an important effort... a lot of administrative aspects were addressed in a short time.”* *“We inform the President of our Faculty and the CIVIS/Erasmus+ office... we have their support and acceptance within a few days.”* Strong administrative involvement was described as crucial: *“It is all about the administrative support”* and *“the administrative staff is very helpful.”* At the same time, some noted communication challenges, such as *“difficulty to connect and find correct partners”* or internal communication being *“drowned in the mass of information.”*
- **Clarity, complexity, and consistency of procedures.** Respondents offered mixed experiences regarding clarity. Some described the process as very clear and well-structured, with comments like *“the administrative steps are clear”* and *“the process is transparent, well-communicated, and easy to follow.”* Others, however, found it ambiguous or inconsistent, stating *“each faculty has different rules”* or *“discussion has not yet started... it is not clear whether a BIP can be included in the main program.”* Certain procedures, such as *“peer-reviewed application with external references”* or *“evaluation by external evaluators,”* added further formal layers.

The three major aspects: **approval pathways**, **administrative support**, and **clarity of procedures** shape coordinators' experiences and directly influence the speed and quality of BIP implementation.

Furthermore, coordinators were asked to identify the **main challenges (Q10) encountered when validating, accrediting, and embedding CIVIS BIPs within existing academic and administrative frameworks.** The responses highlight obstacles related to procedures, recognition mechanisms, workload, coordination, and institutional integration, providing a basis for understanding where support and improvement may be needed.

- **Institutional and administrative constraints.** Many coordinators described structural limitations and slow decision-making processes that hinder BIP validation. In several universities, the absence of a formal framework for BIP accreditation or curriculum flexibility makes integration difficult, with one coordinator noting that the *“curriculum is not flexible”* and central policy is *“non-friendly towards BIPs.”* Slow internal procedures, often involving multiple committees, were also identified as obstacles, as approvals *“involve multiple layers leading to extended waiting times”* and in some cases course creation requires several internal bodies to sign off, leading to processes that *“did not match the application timeline very well.”* In a few institutions, structural inertia further delays innovation, where *“better not changing anything”* reflects a tendency to preserve existing procedures.
- **Bureaucratic workload and misalignment with university systems.** Heavy administrative demands and inconsistencies with existing academic systems create significant pressure on staff. Several coordinators mentioned that the validation process *involves “extensive documentation, cross-checking,*

and alignment with various internal and EU regulations," making the workload substantial. Others highlighted misalignment with institutional systems, such as BIPs not fitting the university's "traditional semester-based system," or academic calendars that require mobility and grading to be completed before certain dates, leading to "critical administrative obstacles in ensuring smooth accreditation." Additionally, financial and administrative procedures have become increasingly complex, with financing described as "constantly more bureaucratic and draconic" complicating even routine aspects like advertising the courses or processing expenses.

- **Resource and staffing challenges.** Limited financial and human resources constitute another major challenge. Many coordinators pointed out insufficient budgets that affect mobility, teaching, and logistics, noting that "available financial resources are not always sufficient," which creates uncertainty in planning. At several institutions, there is "no dedicated support staff," meaning responsibilities are spread across already overloaded administrative and academic teams, slowing down communication and decision-making. Staffing constraints also affect academic engagement: teachers often receive no compensation or recognition, making it "difficult to find available teachers or researchers willing to take part," especially in contexts where BIPs do not match existing course structures. Building teams capable of delivering both online and field components with partners across institutions was also reported as a challenge.
- **Recognition, curriculum integration, and academic compatibility.** Embedding BIPs within formal curricula remains challenging due to diverse internal rules and recognition procedures. Some institutions require students to obtain approval from curriculum commissions to have the BIP accredited, while others recognise BIPs only as "supplementary activities" rather than equivalent academic courses, limiting their impact. Differences across faculties, where "each faculty has different rules," and constraints requiring BIPs to match existing teaching units restrict innovation and make it difficult to introduce interdisciplinary or "out-of-the-box" content. In addition, concerns about academic standards arise when BIPs include transdisciplinary entry requirements, causing uncertainty about guaranteeing student progression.

Despite these challenges, a few coordinators also reported positive examples of straightforward recognition, such as: "Validation is easy and well-structured," "The BIP is already integrated as a formal subject," and "Students present the Transcript of Records... and the grade is included in the file."

Across universities, the validation and recognition of BIPs range from highly efficient and well-supported to complex, unclear, or slow, depending on institutional structures, communication flows, and administrative resources.

3.4. Support received by students and coordinators

This subsection examines students' perceptions of the **level and nature of support received** in relation to their participation in CIVIS BIPs, focusing on both the **timing of support across different stages of the programme lifecycle (Q10)** and the **main areas in which support was experienced (Q11)**. Together, these questions provide insight into how institutional and alliance-level support structures accompany students before, during, and after programme participation.

Students reported **high levels of satisfaction with the support received across all three stages** of the programme lifecycle. As illustrated in **Figure 9**, the highest mean satisfaction score was recorded **during the programme (M = 3.403)**, followed by **after the programme (M = 3.239)** and **before the programme (M = 3.180)**. The consistently high mean values, combined with narrow confidence intervals, indicate that students generally perceived support structures as reliable and effective throughout their engagement with CIVIS BIPs.

Figure 9. Students' satisfaction with the level of support received across different stages of the CIVIS BIP lifecycle

Support **before the programme** was positively evaluated by most respondents, with **81.35%** reporting that they were **rather satisfied (40.10%, n = 245)** or **very satisfied (41.24%, n = 252)**. A smaller proportion expressed **dissatisfaction (18.66%)**, including **4.58% (n = 28)** who were **very dissatisfied**. The mean score (M = 3.180, 95% CI [3.113-3.247]) and moderate dispersion (SD = 0.840) suggest that pre-programme support was generally effective, while also leaving room for improvement in ensuring that all students receive timely and consistent guidance prior to programme start.

Satisfaction with support **during the programme** was particularly strong. Nearly **89.53%** of respondents indicated that they were **rather satisfied (34.53%, n = 211)** or **very satisfied (54.99%, n = 340)**. This stage also recorded the **highest share of very satisfied responses**, reflected in the highest mean score (M = 3.403, 95% CI [3.340-3.465]) and a relatively low standard deviation (SD = 0.788). These results indicate that students felt especially well supported during the active learning and mobility phase, when practical, academic, and logistical needs are most acute.

Support **after the programme** was likewise evaluated positively, with **85.44%** of respondents reporting **satisfaction (rather satisfied: 42.72%, n = 261; very satisfied: 42.72%, n = 261)**. Although slightly lower than during-programme support, the mean score (M = 3.239, 95% CI [3.175-3.030]) remains high, suggesting that follow-up support such as administrative closure, recognition procedures, or access to information after completion was generally perceived as adequate. The presence of **14.56% dissatisfied** responses nonetheless points to the importance of strengthening post-programme communication and follow-up mechanisms.

To complement this temporal analysis, students were asked to indicate the **areas in which they received the most support (Q11)**. As shown in **Figure 10** support was most frequently experienced in **administrative matters**, selected in **43.91% (n = 422)** of responses. This finding aligns closely with the challenges identified in the previous section and suggests that administrative support plays a critical compensatory role in helping students navigate complex procedures.

Figure 10. Main areas of support experienced by students during their participation in CIVIS BIPs

Academic support emerged as the second most prominent category (**33.19%**, **n = 319**), underlining the importance of teaching staff, academic coordinators, and supervisors in supporting students' learning experiences. Together, administrative and academic support account for more than three quarters of all reported support experiences, highlighting their centrality within the CIVIS BIP support ecosystem.

Other forms of support were reported less frequently but remain relevant. **Help with personal needs and problems** was selected in **9.16%** (**n = 88**) of responses, while **support from student initiatives** accounted for **8.53%** (**n = 82**). More specialised forms of support, such as **help with inclusion needs** (**2.81%**, **n = 27**) and **mental health support** (**1.25%**, **n = 12**), were reported by a small minority of respondents. While these lower frequencies may reflect limited need among the surveyed population, they also point to areas in which visibility, accessibility, or awareness of support services could be further enhanced.

Overall, the findings from these two questions (Q10 and Q11) indicate that CIVIS BIPs are underpinned by **robust and multi-layered support structures**, with particularly strong performance during the active phase of programme delivery. **Administrative and academic support** emerge as the primary pillars of this system, effectively accompanying students through complex procedural and learning-related demands. At the same time, the slightly lower satisfaction levels before and after the programme, together with the limited visibility of specialised support services, suggest opportunities to further strengthen continuity of support across the full programme lifecycle. Enhancing pre-programme guidance, post-programme follow-up, and awareness of inclusion and well-being services may contribute to an even more comprehensive and student-centred support framework within CIVIS BIPs.

3.4.2. Support received by BIP coordinators

Overall, as **Figure 11** shows, **administrative and financial support** stand out as the strongest areas. Administrative support was reported as available by **all respondents (100%)**, with no indications of lack or irrelevance, suggesting a consistently effective administrative framework. Financial support was also rated very positively, with **97.8%** of respondents indicating that it was provided, and only a marginal share reporting it as not available or not applicable. These findings point to a solid institutional and funding structure underpinning the BIPs.

Figure 11. Types of support received by BIP coordinators

Coordinators most commonly described **financial support** in terms of **lumpsum CIVIS BIP funding** and **Erasmus+ mobility grants**, which covered key costs such as student and staff mobility, accommodation, catering, field trips, transport, and organisational expenses. Financial support was typically provided by CIVIS offices, Erasmus+/International Relations Offices, Rectorates, or Faculty-level structures. Coordinators valued especially the **predictability and scope of funding**. However, several respondents highlighted **timing issues**, noting that funds were sometimes transferred late in the academic year or after implementation, creating challenges for advance payments and cash flow. Some also mentioned **delays in post-BIP reimbursements** due to platform or inter-institutional registration issues.

Administrative support was described as **extensive and central to BIP implementation**, covering tasks such as student registration, learning agreements, mobility documentation, financial paperwork, coordination between partner universities, accommodation arrangements, and certification. This support was mainly provided by International Relations Offices, CIVIS institutional coordinators, Erasmus+ offices, faculty secretariats, and mobility officers. Many coordinators emphasised the **responsiveness, availability, and problem-solving role** of administrative staff, often describing the support as “*continuous*” or “*very strong*.” At the same time, a recurring theme concerns the **complexity and bureaucratic load of procedures**, with several respondents noting that administrative processes are time-consuming and require significant effort from academic coordinators, sometimes detracting from pedagogical tasks.

Support related to **dissemination and technical aspects** shows a slightly more differentiated picture. **Dissemination support** was confirmed by **73.9% of respondents**, while nearly **one fifth (19.5%)** reported not receiving such support. **Technical support** follows a similar pattern, with **67.3%** confirming its availability, **28.2%** indicating it was not available. This suggests that while technical support is present in most cases, it remains an area with room for improvement, particularly for programmes relying on digital or blended formats.

Dissemination support was described in relation to **promotion of BIPs through CIVIS and institutional channels**, including CIVIS and university websites, mailing lists, social media, newsletters, and partner university networks. This support was typically provided by CIVIS communication teams, institutional CIVIS hubs, International Relations Offices, and partner universities. Coordinators generally expressed **high satisfaction with dissemination efforts**, particularly when **promotion was coordinated across multiple institutions**. However, some respondents noted that dissemination could be more visible or better coordinated, especially during the student application phase, and suggested improvements such as centralised calls for students or stronger promotion at home universities.

Technical support was most often associated with **access to and assistance with digital platforms**, including CIVIS Moodle, the CIVIS mobility platform, Zoom, institutional IT systems, Wi-Fi, and laboratory or classroom infrastructure. Coordinators frequently described this support as **functional, reliable, and sufficient**,

particularly when it came to setting up courses, managing online components, and supporting hybrid delivery. In many cases, respondents stated that no specific technical support was needed, indicating that **existing systems worked adequately**. Nevertheless, several coordinators raised concerns about the **user-friendliness of the CIVIS mobility platform**, describing it as time-consuming, complex to manage, and occasionally problematic for student enrolment and status updates.

The most uneven results are observed for **pedagogical support** where only **39.1% of respondents reported receiving such support**, while a majority (**54.3%**) indicated that it was not available and **6.6%** considered it not applicable. This contrasts sharply with the strong administrative and financial backing and suggests that structured pedagogical guidance, instructional design support, or teaching-related assistance is less systematically embedded across BIPs. In many cases, coordinators indicated that **no formal pedagogical support was provided or required**, as teaching design and delivery were handled collaboratively by partner universities. Where pedagogical support was mentioned, it typically took the form of planning and coordination meetings, collaboration among academic staff, peer exchange of teaching materials, and training sessions or workshops organised by CIVIS on blended learning, digital tools, or innovative pedagogies. Some coordinators highlighted the value of **interdisciplinary teamwork** and **peer-to-peer collaboration** as an implicit form of pedagogical support.

Overall, while satisfaction with pedagogical aspects was high, the data suggest that pedagogical support is less structured and less institutionalised than administrative or financial support. The analysis indicates that while BIPs benefit from robust administrative and financial support, greater emphasis could be placed on strengthening pedagogical, technical, and dissemination support to ensure more balanced and comprehensive institutional backing.

4

MOBILITY EXPERIENCE

4.1. Administrative and organisational aspects of the mobility process

This subsection focuses specifically on students' experiences with the **administrative and organisational dimensions of physical mobility** within CIVIS BIPs, analysing students' **overall assessment of the process of organising and completing their mobility (Q12)** and the **main challenges encountered in this process (Q13)**. Importantly, the results presented here relate exclusively to information provision, administrative procedures, financial arrangements, and institutional support mechanisms associated with mobility, and do not address the teaching and learning experience during the physical mobility, which is examined separately in another section of the report.

Overall, students reported a **strongly positive evaluation of the administrative and organisational aspects of the mobility process**. As illustrated in **Figure 12**, most respondents rated the process of organising and completing their mobility as **good (40.43%, n = 247)** or **very good (49.43%, n = 302)**. In contrast, **7.20% (n = 44)** assessed the process as **poor** and only **1.15% (n = 7)** as **very poor**. A small proportion of respondents (**1.80%, n = 11**) indicated that the question was **not applicable**, reflecting cases in which participation in the BIP was supported through funding mechanisms other than Erasmus+, such as institutional or alternative mobility schemes¹.

Figure 12. Students' overall assessment of the administrative and organisational aspects of the mobility process

The resulting mean score (**M = 3.435, 95% CI [3.380-3.491]**), combined with a relatively low standard deviation (**SD = 0.704**) and standard error (**SE = 0.028**), indicates a high degree of consistency in students' responses. These findings suggest that, from an administrative and organisational perspective, the mobility component of CIVIS BIPs is generally perceived as **well structured, clearly supported, and effectively coordinated**.

A more detailed examination of the **specific challenges related to the mobility process (Q13)** provides further insight into the areas where students encountered constraints. As shown in **Figure 13**, the most frequently reported challenge concerned the **information received about the mobility process**, selected in **35.06% (n = 271)** of responses. Closely related to this, **33.89% (n = 262)** of responses pointed to challenges linked to the **timing of financial disbursement**, specifically regarding **when the money was received**. These results

¹ This category refers to students whose participation in the BIP was financed through funding mechanisms other than Erasmus+. This includes students from the University of Glasgow, the University of Lausanne, or from one of the six CIVIS Associate Partner universities in Africa, as well as students from Erasmus+ CIVIS universities who participated using institutional or alternative funding sources rather than Erasmus+ mobility funding.

underline the importance of **clarity**, **predictability**, and **timeliness** in administrative communication and financial procedures.

Figure 13. Main administrative and financial challenges encountered during the mobility process

Financial adequacy also emerged as a significant issue, with **20.70% (n = 160)** of responses identifying the **amount of money received** as a challenge. While less frequently selected, the **“Other”** category (**10.35%, n = 80**) captures a range of individual or context-specific issues that further illustrate the diversity of administrative arrangements and funding pathways across participating institutions.

From a statistical perspective, the distribution of responses (**M = 2.195, SD = 1.033, SE = 0.037, 95% CI [2.123-2.268]**) reflects moderate variability in students' experiences. This variability is consistent with differences in national funding rules, institutional administrative practices, and the coexistence of Erasmus+ and non-Erasmus+ mobility pathways within CIVIS BIPs.

Taken together, the findings from Q12 and Q13 point to a **mature and generally effective administrative framework for mobility**, which is nonetheless characterised by recurring pressure points related to **information flows and financial arrangements**. While these challenges do not substantially detract from students' overall positive assessment of the mobility process, they highlight areas where further harmonisation, earlier communication, and increased transparency could enhance predictability and reduce uncertainty for mobile students.

From an implementation perspective, these results underscore the importance of **clear, timely, and coordinated administrative communication**, particularly about funding conditions and payment timelines. Addressing these aspects may further strengthen the administrative dimension of CIVIS mobility and contribute to a more secure and confidence-building experience for students undertaking physical mobility within BIPs.

It is important to contextualise these findings in relation to the regulatory framework governing Erasmus+ mobility funding. The **amount of Erasmus+ financial support** is regulated by the Erasmus+ Programme framework and therefore falls **outside the direct control of CIVIS and its member universities**. While students' concerns regarding the adequacy of funding are clearly reflected in the data, these should be understood as **structural constraints of the Erasmus+ funding model**, rather than as shortcomings of CIVIS mobility implementation.

At the same time, CIVIS has actively engaged in **advocacy and policy dialogue** at European level to raise awareness of students' financial needs in the context of blended and physical mobility and will continue to represent the **student perspective** in discussions on the evolution of Erasmus+ funding schemes. In this sense, the findings of the survey provide valuable empirical input to ongoing efforts to ensure that mobility funding remains aligned with the real costs and inclusiveness objectives of European university cooperation.

4.2. Green mobility

This subsection analyses students' engagement with **green travel options** in the context of CIVIS BIPs, drawing on the quantitative uptake data (Q14) and the extensive qualitative material provided by students who either opted for green travel (Q15) or decided against it (Q16). The focus is placed on **administrative, logistical, financial, and temporal dimensions of mobility**, rather than on teaching and learning experiences during the physical mobility period.

Overall uptake of green travel among respondents remains limited. Only **18.0% (n = 110)** of students reported using green travel, while a clear majority (**82.00%, n = 501**) did not. This distribution indicates that, despite increased policy attention to sustainability within European mobility schemes, green travel has not yet become a routine or default option in the practical context of BIP physical mobility.

At the same time, the qualitative responses from students who did choose green travel reveal a **strongly positive and reflective engagement** with this option when conditions allow. Many respondents frame their decision explicitly in terms of **environmental responsibility and personal values**, referring to sustainability as a guiding principle: *"it is the right thing to do,"* or simply *"environment."* In several cases, this value-based motivation is reinforced by thematic coherence, particularly where sustainability or climate issues were addressed within the BIP itself.

Beyond normative considerations, green travel is frequently described as an **experiential enhancement of mobility**. Students report that travelling by train or bus allowed them to *"see the way," "visit more Europe,"* or experience mobility as a gradual and immersive transition rather than a rapid displacement. In these accounts, the journey itself becomes meaningful, contributing to reflection, cultural exposure, and a stronger sense of international engagement.

Practical advantages also feature prominently in positive accounts, particularly where **infrastructure and connectivity are supportive**. Students highlight the comfort and usability of trains, noting that they offer *"more comfort and more space"* and make it *"easier to work"* while travelling. Such responses are especially common for routes with direct or reliable rail connections, where green travel is perceived as manageable and, in some cases, comparable to flying in terms of overall effort.

However, even among students who reported a positive green travel experience, willingness to repeat the choice is often framed as **conditional**. Respondents frequently qualify their answers with references to **distance and route-specific feasibility**, stating that it *"depends on the location"* or that green travel *"worked well"* in this instance but might not be realistic elsewhere. **Financial conditions** are repeatedly highlighted, with several students explicitly noting that they would choose green travel again *"only if the money is available when booking,"* pointing to the challenge of covering higher upfront costs before reimbursement.

Administrative and procedural issues further complicate these otherwise positive experiences. Some students report having used greener modes of transport but encountering difficulties in having them recognised or reimbursed or not knowing how to claim the green travel top-up. In such cases, green travel is described as **encouraged in principle but difficult to operationalise in practice**: *"I never received information on how to claim,"* or *"it was not possible to apply during or at the end."* These experiences suggest that procedural uncertainty can undermine motivation, even among students strongly inclined toward sustainable mobility.

The responses of students who did not use green travel deepen the understanding of these constraints. Across the dataset, **time emerges as the most pervasive barrier**. Many respondents describe green travel as requiring several additional days, which they could not accommodate due to tightly structured academic calendars, examination periods, compulsory attendance requirements, or employment obligations. In the context of relatively short physical mobility periods, extended travel time is often perceived as disproportionate: green travel would have *"taken days"* or been *"too long compared to the time spent"* at the host institution.

Distance and geography further intensify these time constraints. Students travelling between peripheral regions, across very long distances, or to island destinations frequently describe green travel as practically unavailable. In such cases, **air travel is framed not as a preference but as a necessity**: *“air travel was the only practical means.”* Several respondents add that they might consider green travel for closer destinations, but not under the specific geographical conditions of their BIP.

Financial considerations constitute a second major barrier. Many students report that greener alternatives – particularly long-distance rail travel – were more expensive than flying, even when green travel top-ups were available. Students frequently note that *“train tickets were more expensive than plane tickets,”* and that additional costs linked to longer journeys (overnight accommodation, meals, or missed workdays) further reduced feasibility. For some, the difficulty lies not only in total cost but also in liquidity constraints, with respondents explicitly calling for the ability to *“receive money up front.”*

A further recurring theme concerns **awareness and guidance**. A significant number of students state that they were *“not being aware”* of green travel options, eligibility criteria, or claiming procedures, or that they lacked concrete support in identifying feasible routes. In these accounts, green travel appears **conceptually attractive but practically daunting**, particularly when compared to the simplicity and predictability of booking a flight. Concerns about reliability, safety, and stress – such as the risk of missed connections or poorly functioning rail infrastructure – reinforce perceptions of green travel as uncertain or burdensome.

Taken together, the findings from Q14-Q16 indicate that limited uptake of green travel is driven less by students' attitudes and more by **structural and operational constraints**. The qualitative material reveals a student population that is often positively disposed toward greener mobility and capable of valuing it as an enriching and meaningful experience, but constrained by time pressures, geographical realities, cost structures, payment timing, and administrative complexity. When green travel is feasible, clearly supported, and realistically funded, it can become a highly valued component of the mobility experience. When these conditions are absent, it is experienced as impractical or inequitable.

From an implementation perspective, the data suggest that increasing green travel uptake within CIVIS BIPs will depend **less on persuasion and more on enabling conditions**. Earlier and clearer communication, practical route-planning support, user-friendly administrative procedures, and incentive mechanisms that function effectively in practice, particularly with respect to payment timing, may reduce avoidable friction and allow a larger share of students to consider greener mobility choices in future programme cycles.⁴

4.3. Satisfaction with key aspects of the physical mobility

This subsection analyses students' satisfaction with several **core logistical and spatial aspects of the physical mobility** component of CIVIS BIPs, namely **accommodation, catering, the location of the courses, and the accessibility of the location (Q17)**. The analysis focuses on conditions shaping students' on-site experience and everyday mobility, rather than on academic content or teaching quality.

Overall, students reported **high levels of satisfaction across all four dimensions**, with mean scores consistently above 3 on a four-point scale, as shown by **Figure 14**. This indicates a broadly positive assessment of the material and spatial arrangements surrounding the physical mobility component of BIPs.

Figure 14. Students' satisfaction with the level of support received across different stages of the CIVIS BIP lifecycle

The **location of the courses** received the highest evaluation, with a mean score of **3.552 (95% CI [3.494-3.609])**. Nearly two-thirds of respondents (**65.96%, n = 403**) reported being **very satisfied**, while a further **26.02% (n = 159)** were **rather satisfied**. Only a small minority expressed dissatisfaction. The relatively low dispersion of responses (**SD = 0.721; SE = 0.029**) suggests a high level of consistency across different host institutions and locations. These results indicate that course venues were generally perceived as well chosen, appropriate for programme activities, and supportive of students' participation during the physical mobility period.

Closely aligned with this finding, satisfaction with the **accessibility of the location** was also very high, with a mean score of **3.476 (95% CI [3.419-3.534])**. A clear majority of students (**58.59%, n = 358**) reported being **very satisfied**, and an additional **33.22% (n = 203)** were **rather satisfied**. The small proportion of dissatisfied responses and the low standard deviation (**SD = 0.725**) indicate that, for most participants, locations were perceived as easy to reach and navigate, both in terms of transport connections and local mobility. This finding is particularly relevant considering the challenges discussed before, suggesting that once students arrived at the host destination, local accessibility conditions were generally favourable.

Students' satisfaction with **accommodation** was also positive, though slightly more heterogeneous. The mean score for this aspect was **3.213 (95% CI [3.144-3.281])**, with **44.68% (n = 273)** of respondents being **very satisfied** and **37.64% (n = 230)** **rather satisfied**. At the same time, accommodation recorded a somewhat higher share of **dissatisfied responses (17.68% combined very and rather dissatisfied)** and greater variability (**SD = 0.867; SE = 0.035**) compared to course location and accessibility. This suggests that while accommodation arrangements were generally appreciated, experiences varied more strongly depending on local housing markets, availability, pricing, and institutional support structures.

A similar pattern emerges for **catering**, which received a mean score of **3.205 (95% CI [3.130-3.279])**. Almost half of respondents (**48.45%, n = 296**) reported being **very satisfied**, while **31.42% (n = 192)** were **rather satisfied**. However, catering also shows the highest dispersion among the four aspects (**SD = 0.939; SE = 0.038**) and the largest proportion of **dissatisfied responses (20.13% combined)**. This variability likely reflects differences in local food provision, pricing, dietary options, and access to affordable meals across host locations.

Taken together, the results of Q17 indicate that students' satisfaction with the **physical and logistical environment of CIVIS BIP mobility** is consistently high, particularly regarding **course locations and accessibility**, which appear to be key strengths across the Alliance. Accommodation and catering are also evaluated positively overall, but with greater variability, pointing to context-dependent differences between host institutions and destinations.

From an implementation perspective, these findings suggest that continued attention to **local logistics, housing support, and food accessibility** may further enhance students' on-site experience, especially in

destinations characterised by high living costs or limited short-term accommodation availability. At the same time, the strong evaluations of course location and accessibility provide evidence of effective local planning and coordination, contributing positively to the overall quality and inclusiveness of the physical mobility experience within CIVIS BIPs.

5

**TEACHING AND LEARNING
EXPERIENCE**

5.1. Implementation of teaching and learning activities

When asked about the **implemented activities (Q12, coordinators)**, despite the diversity of terminology used, the learning and teaching activities implemented across the BIPs can be grouped into a limited number of consistent categories, indicating a **high degree of convergence in pedagogical approaches**.

Lectures and **expert-led sessions** were the most frequently implemented activities and included introductory and thematic lectures (covering topics such as localisation, urban nature, bioinformatics, artificial intelligence, and heritage), as well as guest lectures and online or hybrid lecture formats. These activities played a key role in providing conceptual grounding and establishing a shared knowledge base among participants.

Workshops and **hands-on activities** were also widely implemented and constituted a core component of many BIPs. These activities encompassed practical workshops, hands-on sessions, laboratory work, teaching laboratories, and field-based workshops, and were primarily aimed at supporting applied learning, skills development, and experiential learning. Alongside these, **group work** and **collaborative learning** emerged as one of the most consistent pedagogical elements, including group projects, team-based assignments, collaborative problem-solving, interdisciplinary group work, and project-based learning approaches. Such activities were central to fostering teamwork, interdisciplinarity, and peer learning.

Fieldwork, **study visits**, and **site-based learning** were commonly implemented, particularly in place-based BIPs. These activities included field research, field trips (such as those organised in Naxos), study visits, museum visits, and on-site observations, and contributed to contextualised learning and real-world exposure. Seminars, discussions, and reflective activities were also frequently reported, often in combination with other teaching methods. These formats supported critical thinking, reflection, and the integration of learning experiences through guided discussions, peer exchanges, and reflective sessions.

Even though coordinators mentioned that most of the planned activities were also implemented, there is also a number of activities that were not implemented as they were in the initial planning. Across responses (Q12), the reasons for non-implementation are highly repetitive and can be grouped into a small number of categories:

- a) **time constraints:** most frequently cited reason (*examples: lack of time, scheduling difficulties, short duration of the BIP*);
- b) **organisational and logistical constraints:** common, especially for field or physical activities (*examples: scheduling conflicts, limited availability of spaces or equipment, difficulties coordinating visits or labs, physical mobility constraints*);
- c) **institutional or regulatory constraints:** reported mainly for innovative or interdisciplinary activities (*examples: faculty or university rules, national or institutional regulations, accreditation or curriculum constraints*);
- d) **resource limitations:** mentioned less often but clearly present (*examples: lack of technical resources, lack of infrastructure, limited access to digital tools or labs*);
- e) **pedagogical or design decisions:** intentional choices by coordinators (*examples: preference for other methods, focus on core activities, activity replaced by an alternative format*);
- f) **lack of student preparation or feasibility:** occasional but relevant (*examples: student workload concerns, insufficient prior knowledge, complexity not suitable for the group*).

Students also reported a **very high level of consistency between what was presented or announced beforehand** (in terms of content, format, and organisation) and what they **experienced during the educational activity**, as shown by **Figure 15**. Nearly four out of five respondents indicated that the activity was either 'very similar' to what had been announced (48.45%, n=296) or 'exactly as presented' (31.91%, n=195). A smaller group rated it as 'somewhat similar' (15.06%, n=92), while only a very small minority considered that it matched poorly,

with 3.44% (n=21) saying it was only 'slightly similar' and 1.15% (n=7) stating it was 'not at all similar'.

Statistically, the responses yield a **mean score of 4.056 on a 5-point scale**, where 1 corresponds to 'not at all similar' and 5 to 'exactly as presented'. This average lies clearly above the midpoint and very close to the 'very similar' category, indicating that, overall, participants experienced a **strong alignment between expectations and reality**. The standard deviation of 0.841 suggests relatively low dispersion around this high mean, with most respondents clustered in the upper part of the scale. The 95% confidence interval for the mean, ranging from 3.999 to 4.132, together with a standard error of 0.034, shows that this estimate is statistically precise and robust.

Figure 15. Alignment between design and delivery

Altogether, these results indicate that information provided in advance about the programme (regarding content, format, and organisation) was **generally reliable and accurate**, and that participants felt their **expectations were well met** by the actual educational activities.

5.2. Quality and relevance of teaching and learning activities

Students reported a **very high level of satisfaction with the quality of learning and teaching activities** in the programme, as shown by **Figure 16**. Out of 611 respondents, **33.72% (n=206)** were **rather satisfied**, and **57.77% (n=353)** were **very satisfied**. The mean satisfaction score was **3.452** on a 4-point scale, with a 95% confidence interval of 3.391 to 3.512, indicating consistently high satisfaction. Only 8.51% of respondents expressed any level of dissatisfaction, suggesting that teaching and learning quality is a strong aspect of the program overall.

Students highlighted a wide range of learning activities as particularly relevant (Q19), with a strong emphasis on those that were **practical, applied, and interactive**. The most frequently mentioned activities were **hands-on practical work** and **laboratory sessions**, where students could directly apply theoretical concepts. One participant noted that "laboratory work was my favourite moment, we learned a lot," while another emphasised that "hands-on lab work." **Method-specific activities**, such as **using specialised instruments and techniques**, were also praised; for example, a respondent wrote that "the use of FTIR spectroscopy was highly relevant." These experiences were perceived as highly meaningful because they allowed participants to engage with real scientific and professional practices rather than only learning about them in abstract terms.

Figure 16. Satisfaction with the quality of learning and teaching activities

Fieldwork and **learning in real-world contexts** were also identified as especially valuable. Participants repeatedly mentioned **field trips**, **in-field teaching**, and **sampling activities** as particularly relevant. One student highlighted practical activities such as “*sampling sand from a dune*,” while another stressed that “*field work, especially when the professors were with us*,” made the learning experience more concrete. Others referred more generally to “*field research and field trips*” and “*practical experiences in labs and field trips*.” These activities helped students connect course content to authentic settings and real environmental, clinical, or social conditions, and were often described as moments when the relevance of their learning became especially clear.

In addition, **structured workshops** and **skill-building sessions** were frequently cited, particularly those focused on academic and professional competencies. **Workshops on academic publishing** and **scientific writing** were repeatedly mentioned as highly useful; for instance, one participant described “*one of the most relevant learning activities [...] was the workshop on academic publishing strategies, which gave us practical insights*,” while another appreciated “*practical activities like trying to write the title or the abstract of a scientific paper*” as part of an in-field teaching activity. Similarly, “*hands-on bioinformatics practice*” and “*hands-on workshop and data analysis*” were noted as activities that built concrete methodological and technical skills. These sessions were viewed as directly transferable to students' future studies and careers, offering clear guidance on how to write, structure, and disseminate research.

More **traditional formats**, such as **lectures**, **seminars**, and **expert talks** were considered most relevant when they were clearly connected to current issues, real cases, or cutting-edge research, and when they allowed for interaction. Respondents referred positively to “*lectures*” and “*seminars about relevant sociological issues*,” as well as to “*conferences*” and invited expert sessions. These were appreciated particularly when they complemented practical components and helped frame the broader context of the field.

Collaborative and interactive learning formats were another important element of perceived relevance. Participants pointed to “*group projects during the online part of the course*,” “*group presentation*,” and “*teamwork*” as meaningful activities. Such tasks fostered critical thinking, communication, and exposure to diverse perspectives, especially within international and interdisciplinary groups. As one respondent summarised, “*group work and networking*” were themselves valuable components of the learning experience.

Some participants further underscored the relevance of **reflection and personal development activities**, which encouraged them to think about their own experiences, resilience, and future roles. For example, one activity was described as “*an activity where I reflected on a difficult situation that I overcame, learning how to be more resilient*.” These elements supported not only academic growth but also personal and professional identity formation.

Finally, **cultural and institutional visits** were also highlighted for their contribution to the perceived relevance of the programme. While mentioned less frequently than labs or fieldwork, **visits to museums, archaeological sites, hospitals**, and other institutions were valued for helping to situate learning within broader social, cultural, and institutional frameworks. One participant, for instance, cited “*museum visit*” and another “*visits to historical and archaeological sites*” as among the most relevant activities, noting how they contextualised and enriched the theoretical content covered in class.

From the respondents' perspective, ‘*relevant*’ tends to mean learning activities that clearly **bridge theory and practice**, are **directly useful for their academic or professional future**, and **feel authentic to real-world contexts**. Comments indicate that students see relevance in activities where they can apply knowledge, practice concrete skills (e.g. writing, analysis, use of tools), and engage actively rather than passively. Similarly, the examples provided show that respondents value activities that prepare them for how work is actually done in their discipline. As one student put it, “*this hands-on approach made the learning experience more engaging and meaningful*,” a sentiment echoed across many responses mentioning “*practical experiences on the lab equipment and fieldwork*,” “*hands-on activities, lab visits, and field research*,” and similar formulations.

In this sense, relevance is not just about interest or enjoyment, but about **perceived applicability, professional preparation**, and **meaningful engagement** with the subject matter. These findings suggest that the programme's strongest elements lie in its experiential, applied, and interactive components, particularly where they are clearly linked to students' future academic or career trajectories.

When asked to name up to three aspects they most enjoyed about the programme, **Figure 17** shows that participants clearly emphasised the **relational and collaborative dimensions**, alongside **content and pedagogy**. The most frequently selected aspect was **communication and collaboration with fellow students (n=449; 27.70%)**, highlighting how strongly students valued peer interaction, international networking, and working together in multicultural, interdisciplinary groups. The second most common response was **communication and collaboration with teachers (n=360; 22.21%)**, suggesting that students particularly appreciated the approachability, support, and constructive engagement with the teaching staff.

Figure 17. Main aspects enjoyed about the programmes

Academic dimensions were also central to participants' enjoyment. **Content** was selected **326 times (20.11%)**, indicating that the topics covered aligned well with students' interests and expectations. **Teaching practices and methods (n=264; 16.29%)** were also frequently appreciated, pointing to the perceived quality of the pedagogical approaches used (e.g. interactive teaching, practical components, blended formats). **Learning outcomes** were mentioned **209 times (12.89%)**, showing that many participants considered they had acquired meaningful competences through the programme. Only a very small proportion of responses fell into the ‘*Other*’ category (n=13; 0.80%), suggesting that the predefined options captured the main sources of satisfaction effectively.

A total of **1621 choices** were recorded across all respondents (611), with each student able to select up to three aspects. On average, participants selected **about three aspects (mean = 2.994)**, with a standard deviation of 1.354, indicating some variation in how many aspects individuals chose but with most close to the maximum of three. The 95% confidence interval for the mean ranges from 2.926 to 3.056, which statistically confirms that, in the wider population of programme participants, students typically identify close to three different aspects they enjoyed most.

This pattern reinforces the interpretation that satisfaction with the programme is not driven by a single factor, but by a combination of positive experiences with peers, teachers, content, teaching methods, and the learning gains achieved.

5.3. Active learning and student participation

When asked on the degree of **active participation** reported during teaching and learning activities (Q12), coordinators reflected on how participants were engaged and the extent to which the activities supported interaction and involvement. The reflections include insights into the **strategies used for participation, observed limitations, instances of reluctance or low engagement, and suggestions for enhancing future involvement**. These findings offer a nuanced understanding of what facilitated active participation, as well as the areas where further refinement or support may be beneficial.

How participants were involved: across BIPs, students were highly engaged through a variety of interactive and practice-based activities. These included:

- **Collaborative problem-solving and group case studies**, where students worked in mixed international teams to analyse real-world scenarios, negotiate solutions, or co-create outputs (e.g., group proposals, impact chains, localisation projects, BIP research reports).
- **Hands-on fieldwork**, such as hydrological measurements, geomorphological mapping using RTK-GNSS, OSL sampling, drone photogrammetry, and site visits in urban nature planning, archaeology, ecology, and biodiversity.
- **Laboratory experiments and practical workshops**, including biophysical techniques, corpus annotation, translation software, and scientific data analysis.
- **Creative or communicative tasks**, such as creating educational videos, preparing posters, developing mini-projects, and presenting research findings.
- **Interactive lectures and roundtables**, with Q&A sessions, digital polling tools, expert interviews, and debates.
- **Peer feedback and reflection activities**, both online and during physical mobility, to deepen understanding and encourage exchange.

Limitations of the activities: across programmes, several recurrent limitations emerged:

- **Uneven contribution and dominance of certain voices**, especially in group work, when experienced or confident students overshadowed others.
- **Differences in prior knowledge** (e.g., digital literacy, theoretical background, fieldwork experience) which led to uneven starting points and reduced engagement for some.
- **Time constraints**, limiting deeper discussion, proper debriefing after break-out rooms, or full participation in hands-on activities due to limited equipment.
- **Administrative or logistical constraints**, such as difficulty organising interviews, field visits, or maintaining continuity in online sessions.
- **Misalignment with virtual delivery**, including reduced spontaneity, cameras off, inconsistent attendance, and challenges in sustaining engagement during long online lectures.
- **Large group sizes**, preventing everyone from participating fully in discussions or Q&A.

Reluctance from participants: several forms of hesitation were identified:

- **Hesitation to speak in front of peers**, particularly in early sessions or when the language of instruction was not their own.
- **Fear of making mistakes**, especially during hands-on or problem-solving activities, which discouraged some from taking initiative.
- **Discomfort with forced positions** in structured debates or when defending unfamiliar viewpoints.
- **Shyness in academic settings**, especially during expert roundtables or in discussions with stakeholders.
- **Reluctance in online settings**, where students could easily remain silent or off-camera, contributing minimally.
- **Uncertainty with unfamiliar tools**, such as corpus-linguistic software, mapping apps, CAT tools, or laboratory equipment.

Ways to improve participation: coordinators suggested numerous strategies to support more balanced and confident student engagement:

- **Clearer structuring of roles** (moderator, notetaker, presenter) within groups to balance contributions.
- **Guiding questions and prompts** to focus group discussions and encourage targeted contributions.
- **Pre-session preparation materials**, such as mini-tutorials, tool demos, or harmonisation exercises to reduce disparities in prior knowledge.
- **Creating a fail-friendly environment**, emphasising experimentation and reducing pressure to be "correct."
- **Smaller working groups or longer breakout sessions**, ensuring more voices are heard and discussions are meaningful.
- **Combining digital tools with verbal interaction**, using polls or chats only as starting points.
- **Greater use of peer evaluation**, rehearsal sessions, or structured reflections to increase accountability.
- **Shorter, better-timed online sessions**, with interactive components rather than long lectures.
- **Better integration of fieldwork**, providing more opportunities for hands-on learning and student-led inquiry.
- **Providing multiple formats for presenting**, accommodating different communication styles (oral, poster, video).

5.4. Assessment and learning outcomes

5.4.1. Format and methods of assessment

Based on the responses provided by BIP coordinators (Q 14), the **formats and methods of assessment** used across the programmes show **considerable diversity**, while still clustering around a set of recurring and well-established approaches. The most frequently reported assessment formats include **written assignments** (such as essays, reports, portfolios, and written exams), **oral presentations** (both individual and group-based), and **continuous assessment methods linked to participation and engagement**. In addition, quizzes and online tests (often administered through digital platforms such as Moodle) were commonly used, alongside **practical and hands-on assessments** connected to workshops, laboratory activities, fieldwork, and project-based tasks. **Peer review**, **self-assessment**, and **reflective journals** also appear as complementary methods, particularly in BIPs aiming to foster active participation and critical reflection.

Teachers' reflections on these assessment formats are **largely positive** and emphasise their contribution to **student engagement**, **learning depth**, and **skills development**. Participation-based and active assessment methods are frequently described as effective in **encouraging student involvement**, **collaboration**, and **responsibility for learning**. Oral presentations and group projects are highlighted for supporting teamwork,

communication skills, and interdisciplinary exchange, while practical and hands-on assessments are valued for reinforcing applied learning and real-world relevance. Online quizzes and written tests are generally perceived as efficient and well-organised tools for checking understanding and monitoring progress, especially in blended or intensive formats.

At the same time, teachers also report some **challenges related to assessment design and implementation**. Several reflections point to **workload and time constraints**, noting that certain assessment formats, particularly those involving multiple components or intensive participation, can be demanding for both students and staff. In a few cases, **participation-based assessment was described as difficult to manage or uneven in terms of student contribution**, and some respondents indicated that students could feel overwhelmed. Nevertheless, the overall reflection suggests that **combining diverse assessment methods** – balancing written, oral, practical, and participatory formats – is perceived as a strong practice that aligns well with the pedagogical aims of BIPs and supports meaningful learning outcomes.

From students' point of view, as **Figure 18** shows, they evaluated the assessment methods used in the course **very positively**. Half of the respondents rated them as **'very appropriate'** (50.41%, n=308), and a further **41.90% (n=256)** considered them **'rather appropriate'**. Only a small minority perceived them negatively, with 1.96% (n=1212) indicating they were **'very inappropriate'** and 5.73% (n=35) **'rather inappropriate'**.

Figure 18. Appropriateness of the assessment methods

This distribution yields a **mean score of 3.408** on a 4-point scale, where 1 represents 'very inappropriate' and 4 represents 'very appropriate', indicating that, on average, **students clearly lean towards viewing the assessment methods as appropriate for evaluating what they learned**. The standard deviation of 0.689 suggests relatively low variability in responses, meaning most students cluster around the 'rather appropriate' to 'very appropriate' range rather than being widely dispersed across the scale. Statistically, the 95% confidence interval for the mean lies between 3.353 and 3.462, and the standard error is 0.028, which confirms that this high level of perceived appropriateness is estimated with good precision.

These results indicate that the assessment methods (such as tests, projects, and presentations) were, for most participants, **well aligned with the course learning objectives** and were seen as a **fair and suitable way to evaluate their learning**.

Overall, students described the **assessment of their learning** (Q22, students) as **broadly effective** but highlighted several areas where adjustments could enhance its educational value. On the positive side, many appreciated the **variety and overall fairness of assessment methods**, noting that the mix of tasks captured different skills and learning outcomes. One participant commented that *"assessment was comprehensive and*

fair,” while another valued that *“the presentation at the end [...] encouraged teamwork.”* **Practical and participatory formats** were particularly well received; activities such as group projects, presentations, and applied tasks were seen as closely aligned with what had been taught, with comments such as *“the practical, hands-on approach [...] made the content engaging and memorable”* illustrating this appreciation. Where assessment criteria and expectations were clearly communicated, students felt more confident and supported, as reflected in remarks like *“the feedback from teachers was clear and helpful.”*

At the same time, respondents pointed to **important areas for improvement**, especially regarding **feedback, clarity, and workload**. Several students reported that **feedback was delayed or missing**, limiting its usefulness for learning, with one noting that *“I never received any feedback on my assessment project,”* and another suggesting that *“It might be helpful to receive more feedback during the preparation process, not just at the end.”* Others stressed the need for **clearer and more consistent assessment guidelines**, particularly for online or hybrid components, suggesting that assessment criteria should be communicated from the beginning. Concerns were also raised about the **balance and timing of assessment tasks**, with some describing the workload as excessive or poorly distributed over time. Comments such as *“heavy assignments”* and *“the course load was way too big from week to week and in the end, the presentation felt too rushed to be anything other than stressing”* suggest that, although the formats themselves were often appropriate, their scheduling and volume sometimes undermined the overall experience.

Altogether, the responses indicate that the assessment approach is generally perceived as fair and pedagogically sound, particularly when it is practical and well explained, but that its effectiveness could be further strengthened by ensuring timely, detailed feedback, clearer criteria from the beginning, and a more balanced distribution of assessment tasks across the programme.

5.4.2. Achievement of learning outcomes

This section presents insights into whether participants **achieved the intended learning outcomes**, with responses indicating a **full (100%) level of attainment**. To understand how this was supported, the analysis is structured around five key approaches that contributed to participants' progress: **(1) structured and scaffolded learning design; (2) continuous feedback, guidance, and tutor support; (3) hands-on, practice-based, and fieldwork activities; (4) collaborative learning, peer interaction, and group work; and (5) the use of digital platforms, resources, and tools**. The reflections highlight how each of these components facilitated learning, while also offering an evidence-based view of the strategies perceived as most effective in enabling participants to reach the desired outcomes.

- **Structured and scaffolding learning design.** Many coordinators supported students through **step-by-step learning pathways**, gradually increasing complexity while providing clear instructions. Examples include structuring the course with *“gradual steps, clear instructions, timely feedback and varied learning formats”* and aligning tasks so students could *“apply theory in practice progressively.”* Preparatory online sessions, flipped-classroom activities, reading packages, and warm-ups were widely used to ensure students built foundational knowledge before advancing.
- **Continuous feedback, guidance, and tutor support. Regular feedback** (both collective and one-to-one) was central across BIPs. Coordinators described *“continuous assessment,” “constant feedback throughout the creation process,”* and *“monitoring, guidance, and immediate instructor support”* as key mechanisms. Several BIPs employed tutors and mentors, who *“guided students through sampling, analysis, and report writing,”* or supported them in writing essays, designing projects, or preparing presentations.
- **Hands-on, practice-based, and fieldwork activities.** A significant number of BIPs relied on **experiential learning** to achieve outcomes, especially in field-oriented disciplines. Students learned through *“data collection, hydrological measurements, drone photogrammetry, geomorphological mapping,”* laboratory experiments, and site visits in ecology, archaeology, linguistics, and pharmacology. These activities helped students directly apply concepts and *“consolidate learning through experience,”* often supported by demonstrations, small-group tutoring, and role assignment.
- **Collaborative learning, peer interaction, and group work.** Learning outcomes were often supported through **team-based work, peer review, and structured collaboration**. Coordinators highlighted group

projects, debates, case analyses, and joint presentations, noting that *“peer interaction and individual reflection contributed to consolidating the outcomes.”* In some BIPs, students worked in **interdisciplinary teams**, benefiting from exchanges across all three levels (bachelor, master, doctoral) or across different universities. Collaboration was reinforced through *“structured debates, peer-review sessions, poster presentations,”* and small-group tasks in both virtual and physical mobility phases.

- **Use of digital platforms, resources, and learning tools.** Support was also provided through **digital learning environments** such as Moodle and specialised tools. Teachers uploaded *“lectures, seminars, recorded sessions, readings, and extra materials,”* enabling students to revisit resources and prepare. Interactive tools (e.g., polls, breakout rooms) and software (GIS, CAT tools, corpus tools like AntConc) helped students practice relevant skills. Several respondents also emphasised the value of *“well-structured online sessions, online workshops, and access to digital resources.”*

Across BIPs, teachers supported students in achieving learning outcomes through a **combination of structured learning design, continuous guidance, experiential and field-based activities, collaborative learning, digital support tools, and alignment of assessments with intended outcomes.** This multi-layered support helped ensure that students could develop both conceptual understanding and practical competences, regardless of differences in prior knowledge or learning environments.

Coordinators reported **relatively few obstacles to students reaching the intended learning outcomes** (Q16), yet several recurring challenges emerged. In some cases, students' **uneven prior knowledge** created disparities in progression, with coordinators noting *“very different profiles of students coming from different studies”* or even a *“lack of basic knowledge of the topics covered.”* Others highlighted **limited engagement**, especially in the virtual phase, where *“limited engagement with online components”* and *“not being participative within the teams or completing quizzes on time”* affected performance. **Time constraints** also played a role, as some participants struggled with *“limited time for data interpretation and analysis for their projects,”* while varying levels of commitment during group work further impacted results. A few programmes faced **external or logistical obstacles**, such as *“weather affecting fieldwork activities”* or *“administrative issues (e.g., visas) causing problems for a small number of students.”* In isolated cases, coordinators observed **confidence-related challenges**, such as a *“lack of confidence for the individual exam.”* Overall, while most students successfully reached the learning outcomes, these examples illustrate the practical and pedagogical constraints that occasionally hindered full achievement.

5.4.3. How learning outcomes align with teaching activities and assessment

Coordinators' responses show **full agreement (100%)** that the **learning outcomes were clearly aligned with both the teaching and learning activities and the assessment strategies** (Q17). Further analysis explores how this alignment was achieved, highlighting the intentional connection between **what participants were expected to learn, the activities through which they engaged with the content, and the methods used to assess their progress.** Examples provided by respondents illustrate how specific activities directly supported targeted outcomes and how assessments were designed to **measure the skills and knowledge developed throughout the learning process** (Q18).

In several BIPs, **problem-solving outcomes** were developed through group projects and then evaluated via written reports, ensuring that students demonstrated both analytical and applied STEAM competences. For example, *“the outcome related to STEAM problem-solving was addressed through group projects, then assessed via written reports. Similarly, the outcome targeting critical reflection was supported through individual journals and evaluated based on the depth of analysis.”*

Courses that aimed to enhance **critical reflection and independent learning** assessed these outcomes through individual reflective journals, self-assessment activities, and structured debates, where the depth of analysis and argumentation directly contributed to the evaluation. Other programmes focused on applying theoretical knowledge, learning outcomes were aligned with group presentations, problem-solving workshops, and debates, which allowed instructors to assess students' ability to transfer theory into practice. For example, *“group presentations and problem-solving workshops assessed the ability to apply theoretical*

knowledge in practice, while debates and discussions were linked to outcomes related to critical thinking, communication, and argumentation."

One course used a sequence in which students completed **model-specific quizzes**, followed by team research proposals and presentations; these were all evaluated with a shared rubric, directly reflecting the learning outcomes for conceptual mastery, experimental design, and scientific communication: *"[...] first level of evaluation is a quiz with questions related to that "theoretical" content. Then they work in teams on a research question posed by the teacher, they have to propose how to approach, which experiments, what they can expect from them. Then they make a presentation, upload it before the deadline, they make the presentation and both teacher and team-mates evaluate through a common rubric. (so they know beforehand what they are going to be evaluated for)."*

In geoscience and environmental BIPs, learning outcomes related to **fieldwork competence and environmental analysis** were assessed through hands-on data collection, mapping tasks, research posters, and final presentations, demonstrating students' ability to apply methods and interpret results: *"field sampling and ecological data collection, stakeholder discussions (local authorities, environmental agencies, Orşova shipyard, Iron Gates Natural Park) museum visits (Iron Gates Hydropower I Museum)."*

Transdisciplinary communication outcomes were evaluated through video creation assignments, which assessed both students' conceptual understanding and their ability to communicate complex ideas to non-academic audiences: *"The communication video is the best example, as it tested both knowledge acquisition and transdisciplinary communication. The quizzes tested conceptual knowledge only."*

In **language and linguistics** BIPs, learning outcomes on using **computational or corpus-linguistic tools** were aligned with practical coding or annotation exercises and poster presentations, requiring students to apply the exact skills taught in workshops: *"The outcome "analyse language change patterns using statistical models" aligned with online workshops on statistical modelling techniques, evaluated through research projects where students applied these models to identify linguistic evolution patterns in their chosen historical texts, presenting findings via posters that visualised the statistical analyses."*

DIGITAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT AND SUPPORT

6.1. Use of the Digital Campus

Most respondents (77.5%) reported that they **made use of the CIVIS Digital Campus or other shared digital resources**, such as the Mobility Platform or Moodle, to support their activities. The analysis explores how these tools were **integrated into the learning process**, the **types of support they enabled**, and the **overall contribution of digital resources to the delivery and coordination of the programmes**.

When asked about **features or functionalities and what can be improved** (Q25), coordinators answers were around three thematic categories: **(1) the features and functionalities that participants found most valuable, illustrated with specific examples**; **(2) the features perceived as missing but potentially useful for supporting BIPs**; and **(3) suggestions for improvement to enhance the effectiveness and usability of the digital tools**. This organisation provides a clear overview of how respondents experienced the available functionalities and where further development could strengthen support for BIP implementation.

Most valuable features or functionalities

Across BIPs, coordinators consistently highlighted **CIVIS Moodle as the most valuable tool**, particularly for providing a **centralised space to upload materials, communicate with students, and organise assignments**. Its functionalities – such as forums, quizzes, and automated assessment – enabled continuous interaction, structured learning, and efficient tracking of student progress: *"The most valuable functionalities were the structured course space in CIVIS Moodle and the ability to organize asynchronous discussions and upload diverse learning materials."*

Many programmes also relied on other platforms, mainly **Zoom for synchronous sessions**, with coordinators noting its reliability for live seminars, mentoring activities, and interactive. In several cases, **collaboration tools such as shared online workspaces (Teams/Drive) and breakout rooms** proved particularly valuable for international teamwork; for example, participants co-created real-time group presentations or worked in small multicultural teams during case studies. The **mobility platform** was regarded as **essential for administrative tasks** – such as application management, enrolment tracking, and documentation – though appreciated mainly for **centralising Erasmus procedures**. Together, these tools enabled smooth delivery, communication, and collaboration across institutions.

Missing but useful features

Many coordinators pointed to a **need for greater integration across tools**, noting the burden of switching between Moodle, Zoom, email, external storage platforms, and mobility systems: *"However, integration with video conferencing tools was limited, necessitating the use of external platforms for synchronous sessions. A built-in video tool and calendar synchronization would be useful additions."* A recurring request was for **built-in video conferencing directly in Moodle**, which would eliminate the need for external platforms like Zoom: *"The platform lacks real-time collaborative coding tools which students need to work on programming exercises together. The process of transferring grades between institutions automatically would help reduce the workload for administrators."*

Others mentioned the **absence of centralised hybrid teamwork features**, such as group workspaces dedicated to each team or real-time collaborative tools (e.g., coding environments for computational courses). Coordinators also noted the lack of **unified authentication/logins across CIVIS systems**, which created difficulties for students navigating multiple institutional accounts: *"The current system faces problems with calendar synchronization between CIVIS partner institutions which creates scheduling conflicts between institutions. Students from different universities need to log in multiple times because there is no unified authentication system in place."*

Several programmes expressed the need for **better asynchronous learning functionalities**, including structured peer-feedback tools and more intuitive collaborative whiteboards or polling tools. For assessment, some coordinators requested **remote proctored testing solutions** to allow standardised evaluation across universities. These gaps suggest the need for a more integrated, versatile digital ecosystem adapted to blended mobility formats: *"More interactive features in online sessions (e.g., collaborative whiteboards, quick quizzes, shared rubrics). Stronger support for hybrid teamwork, including better scheduling features and digital spaces dedicated to each group."*

What could be improved?

The most frequent improvement request concerns **streamlining and simplifying the digital and administrative infrastructure**. Coordinators emphasised that the mobility platform is often difficult to navigate, requires too many steps for simple actions (such as changing student status), and is not compatible with many partner universities' systems. Others mentioned that **login processes, notifications, and navigation in Moodle could be made more intuitive**. Programmes relying on multiple digital tools suggested developing a **more user-friendly interface, clearer guidance**, and **short "technical onboarding sessions"** for both staff and students to reduce confusion and delays. Coordinators also pointed to the need for **calendar synchronization, better cross-institutional grade transfer mechanisms**, and **more reliable communication systems**. A few noted broader structural improvements, such as increased funding, greater homogenisation of procedures across universities, or clearer guidelines for learning agreements and certificate processes. Overall, while digital tools are functional, coordinators called for **improved usability, integration**, and **support** to ensure smoother implementation in future BIPs.

6.2. Quality of digital tools and environments

6.2.1. Satisfaction with digital platforms

Overall, participants reported a **good level of satisfaction with the digital tools used in the programme** (Q29), though with some room for improvement. On a 4-point scale (from 'very dissatisfied' to 'very satisfied'), the **digital platform for sharing resources** received an average satisfaction score of **3.290 (N = 611)**, while the **platform for synchronous activities** (e.g. live sessions) scored **3.320 (N = 611)**. Taken together, this yields an overall **mean satisfaction of 3.305**, indicating that, on average, students were clearly **more satisfied than neutral with both types of platforms**, and that the two systems performed at a very similar level in users' eyes. The consistently high mean values suggest that the digital infrastructure generally supported teaching, learning, and communication effectively. At the same time, the fact that the scores are closer to 'satisfied' than to an absolute maximum suggests there remains some scope to enhance usability, reliability, or integration of these tools to further improve the digital learning experience.

As **Figure 19** shows, participants expressed a **high level of satisfaction with the digital platform used for sharing resources**. On a 4-point scale (1 = very dissatisfied, 4 = very satisfied), most respondents rated their experience positively: 43.70% (n=267) were 'rather satisfied' and the same percent, 43.70% (n=267) were 'very satisfied'. Only a small minority reported negative views, with 10.15% (n=62) 'rather dissatisfied' and 2.45% (n=15) 'very dissatisfied'. This distribution results in a mean satisfaction score of 3.286, which lies clearly above the midpoint and close to the 'very satisfied' category, indicating generally positive perceptions of how well the platform supported access to and sharing of learning materials. The standard deviation of 0.745 shows relatively limited variability around this high mean, suggesting that most students shared a broadly similar, positive view rather than opinions being strongly polarised. The estimate is statistically precise, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 3.227 to 3.346 and a standard error of 0.030.

These results indicate that the **platform for sharing resources was functioning effectively for most participants**, while still leaving some scope for incremental improvements in usability, reliability, or organisation to move more respondents to 'very satisfied'.

Figure 19. Level of satisfaction with the digital platforms for synchronous and sharing resources

Participants also reported a **high level of satisfaction with the platform used for synchronous (live) activities**. Almost all respondents were positive: 49.26% (n=301) were 'rather satisfied' and 42.39% (n=259) 'very satisfied'. Only a small minority expressed dissatisfaction, with 6.71% (n=41) 'rather dissatisfied' and 1.64% (n=10) 'very dissatisfied'. These responses result in a mean satisfaction score of 3.324, which is clearly above the midpoint and very close to the 'very satisfied' category, indicating that the live-session platform generally supported teaching and interaction effectively. The standard deviation of 0.672 is relatively low, showing that most students clustered in the satisfied range rather than being divided between very positive and very negative experiences. The estimate is statistically precise, with a 95% confidence interval from 3.271 to 3.377 and a standard error of 0.027, confirming the robustness of this high satisfaction level.

Overall, the findings suggest that the **synchronous platform functioned reliably and was well accepted by participants**, although the small proportion of dissatisfied users indicates some scope for targeted improvements (e.g. stability, usability, or accessibility).

6.2.2. Functionality gaps and improvement needs

Participants identified several **areas where the digital platforms could be improved** (Q30), focusing mainly on **usability, technical performance, integration, and communication features**.

A recurring theme was **usability and navigation**, with some students finding the main learning platform (e.g. CIVIS Moodle) **difficult to orient in at first**; as one respondent noted, *"the CIVIS Moodle was a bit confusing, but after some menu-manoevring all resources could be found."* This suggests that while the necessary materials were ultimately accessible, a **clearer structure and more intuitive interface would reduce friction for users**. It appears that students need clearer initial guidance (short tutorials, welcome videos, screenshots, or a 'start here' section) to become quickly operational. This is an area where relatively low-effort interventions (better instructions, simple guides) could have a noticeable impact.

Stability and performance issues were also mentioned, particularly in relation to **resource sharing and access**. For example, one participant observed that *"the digital platform for sharing resources was sometimes lagging for some people,"* and another remarked that *"there were some problems with Moodle but they were solved during the course,"* indicating that technical glitches, although often resolved, disrupted the learning experience.

A third major theme concerned the **fragmentation of tools and lack of integration**. Students reported having to navigate multiple systems (e.g. Moodle, Teams, separate CIVIS pages, shared drives) and expressed a **clear preference for a more unified environment**. One respondent suggested, *"please look into unifying the CIVIS platforms. There is no need to have two separate pages,"* while another wished for *"a platform in which you can find all the information, the schedule and the homework."* This points to a need for better integration and

centralisation of information, including timetables, assignments, and resources, which would likely reduce confusion, missed information, and time spent navigating.

In addition, participants highlighted the importance of **enhanced communication and organisational features** within the platforms. Suggestions included easier **ways to set up group communication** (*"better communication on the platform, forming a group chat before the mobility"*), **improved tracking of participation** (*"a system that counts how many absences we have made"*), and **more straightforward access to recordings and materials** (*"access to the class recordings in an easier way"*). Students appear to recommend the integration of tools that help them track their own progress and participation. This aligns with broader trends toward learner-centred design and could be mentioned as an opportunity to strengthen self-regulation and responsibility.

Some also mentioned **access and login issues**, such as *"the login did not work all the time and some students had problems with connecting,"* which can create unnecessary barriers, or even anxiety, especially at key moments (e.g. the start of a course, exams, or synchronous sessions). It is worth noting that stabilising access and performance, particularly at peak times, is important not only for efficiency but also for perceived reliability and trust in the digital environment.

Overall, while **satisfaction with the platforms was generally high**, these comments indicate that students would welcome **more user-friendly, reliable, and integrated digital solutions** that centralise information, support smooth communication, and minimise technical and organisational hurdles.

7

CIVIS EDUCATIONAL VALUES AND INTERDISCIPLINARITY

7.1. Reflection of CIVIS values in the programmes

Coordinators indicate full agreement (100%) that the **pedagogical design of the programs reflected the core CIVIS values of civic engagement, societal impact, and European citizenship** (Q19, Q20). The analysis explores how these values were embedded in both the design and delivery of the learning experience, highlighting concrete examples provided by respondents. The analysis illustrates the ways in which learning activities and assessments **promoted active citizenship, encouraged learners to engage with real societal challenges, and fostered a European perspective within the educational process.**

Civic engagement

Across the BIPs, civic engagement was embedded in activities that required students to analyse **real community issues**, interact with **local stakeholders**, and consider their **civic responsibility**. For example, students designed local interventions for environmental sustainability, analysing challenges in their home contexts and proposing feasible community-oriented solutions. Many programmes engaged students directly with local authorities, urban planners, quarry owners, environmental agencies, or civil society organisations, enabling them to understand how academic knowledge connects with real community needs. Simulation games and debates on public policy, rights, and democracy further encouraged students to reflect on civic responsibility, while tasks such as creating public-facing exhibits or communication materials trained them to translate expertise into socially relevant outputs. Through these activities, students were not only exposed to civic issues but **practiced active citizenship in concrete, applied ways.**

Societal impact

The BIPs consistently linked course content to real-world societal challenges, prompting students to **develop solutions with tangible impact**. Many programmes focused on pressing issues such as climate change, geohazards, rare diseases, public health, environmental degradation, or urban participation, requiring students to apply scientific and analytical methods to understand and address these problems. Fieldwork on coastal erosion, biodiversity, or environmental monitoring enabled students to propose evidence-based sustainability initiatives, while workshops on impact chains, risk reduction, or linguistic heritage demonstrated how academic analysis can inform societal resilience and cultural preservation. Students also explored how sociolinguistic or cultural practices relate to identity, ethics, and public policy: for example, through debates on animal rights, bullfighting, vegetarianism, or ritual practices. By grounding learning activities in contemporary challenges and stakeholder engagement, the BIPs strengthened students' **capacity to transform knowledge into socially meaningful action.**

European citizenship

European citizenship was fostered through the **multinational, multicultural, and interdisciplinary nature of the BIPs**, which brought together students and teachers from multiple European universities, often alongside participants from beyond Europe. Students collaborated in mixed-nationality teams, compared EU policy approaches, worked with European scientific data and heritage, and engaged in discussions that highlighted shared values and cultural diversity. Many programmes explicitly addressed themes central to European identity, such as rights, democracy, multilingualism, linguistic heritage, public engagement, and cultural diversity. The comparative analysis of European cases, whether in public policy, environmental management, linguistic change, or intercultural mediation, helped students recognise both the unity and diversity of European societies. Through joint mobility, interdisciplinary teamwork, and cross-border collaboration, students experienced what it means to participate in a broader European academic and civic community, **strengthening their sense of belonging and mutual understanding.**

At the other side of the analysis, **Figure 20** shows that students perceived a **very strong alignment between the programme they attended and the CIVIS values of civic engagement, societal impact, and European citizenship**. Almost 12.5% (n=76) considered that these values were reflected at least 'to some extent', with 48.77% (n=298) indicating that the programme reflected them 'to a very great extent' and a further 37.81% (n=231) 'to a great extent'. Only a very small minority indicated that the CIVIS values were barely or not at all present, with 0.49% (n=3) answering 'not at all' and 0.49% (n=3) 'to a small extent'.

Figure 20. Extent to which BIPs reflected the CIVIS values of civic engagement, societal impact, and European citizenship

This pattern is reflected in the statistical indicators. The **mean score is 4.339** on a 5-point scale, where 1 corresponds to 'not at all' and 5 to 'to a very great extent'. This high average lies clearly in the upper end of the scale, between 'to a great extent' and 'to a very great extent', indicating that, overall, **participants strongly agreed that the program embodied CIVIS values**. The standard deviation of 0.750 shows relatively limited dispersion around this high mean, suggesting that most respondents shared this positive view rather than opinions being widely spread. The 95% confidence interval for the mean, from 4.279 to 4.398, together with a standard error of 0.030, indicates that this estimate is statistically precise and robust. These results suggest that the programmes were widely perceived as **successfully integrating civic engagement, societal impact, and European citizenship into its design and delivery**, and that these dimensions were clearly **visible and meaningful to participants**.

7.2. Challenge-based learning and impact on engagement

Students generally perceived that the **programmes included substantial elements of challenge-based learning**, as **Figure 21** shows, where students work on real-world problems linked to CIVIS focus areas such as health, climate, or cities. A clear majority indicated that these elements were present at least to a moderate degree: 32.57% (n=199) answered 'to a great extent' and 29.79% (n=182) 'to a very great extent', together accounting for over 60% of respondents. A further 25.70% (n=157) considered that challenge-based learning was included 'to some extent'. Only a small minority reported low or no presence of such elements, with 7.69% (n=47) selecting 'to a small extent' and 4.26% (n=26) 'not at all'.

Results show a **mean score of 3.759** on a 5-point scale, where 1 corresponds to 'not at all' and 5 to 'to a very great extent', indicating that, on average, **participants perceived a solid integration of challenge-based components in their programme**. The standard deviation of 1.091 suggests a somewhat broader spread of views than for some other items, implying that while many students experienced strong challenge-based elements, others encountered them less systematically, possibly reflecting variation between individual programs or courses. The 95% confidence interval, from 3.673 to 3.846, and the standard error of 0.044 indicate that this positive estimate is statistically robust.

Figure 21. Extent to which BIPs included elements of challenge-based learning

Overall, these findings suggest that **challenge-based learning linked to CIVIS priority areas is a visible and appreciated feature of the programmes**, though there remains some room to make such elements more consistently embedded across all offerings.

Students' descriptions of **how challenge-based and CIVIS-related elements affected them** (Q28) point to a **clear positive impact on both engagement and learning outcomes**. Many reported that these components made the learning experience more meaningful and motivating, with one participant noting that they "*focusing on real cases [...] made the learning process much more meaningful*" and "*encouraged me to actively participate, ask questions, and apply the concepts to my own [...] projects*," suggesting not just higher participation, but deeper, self-directed engagement. Working on authentic tasks, with real-world problems and concrete cases, was repeatedly highlighted as crucial for this effect, connecting theory with practice and understanding the societal significance of what was being studied. For example, students referred to working on real cases during the workshops and addressing highly relevant topics, explaining that this helped them see the direct relevance of what they were studying and strengthened the link between theory and practice.

Beyond motivation, respondents emphasised that these elements supported the **development of higher-order skills**. Several mentioned that they "*learned how to put research hypothesis into a real proposal*" and carried out tasks that "*not only required theoretical understanding but also critical thinking, interdisciplinary collaboration, and problem-solving*" through activities that required designing projects, proposals, or solutions to complex problems. At the same time, **collaboration and intercultural exchange** were described as integral to the learning gains: one student valued "*the very diverse point of each student with their complex experience mixed into a productive compost of knowledge that I am using as we speak in my further research*," while another highlighted "*people from many different fields worked together for the same final goal*" as central to their learning.

Overall, these findings suggest that challenge-based and CIVIS-oriented components not only increased students' engagement but also **deepened their understanding of complex issues and strengthened key transversal skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, and teamwork**. The impact of challenge-based components is strongest on the quality of engagement: **students become more proactive, reflective, and willing to extend learning to their own contexts**, rather than simply more active in class. Also, students clearly perceive gains in higher-order competencies: critical thinking, problem-solving, and the ability to translate ideas into concrete proposals, indicating that these activities support key graduate attributes. Finally, by bringing diverse disciplinary and cultural perspectives together around real-world topics, these elements effectively operationalise CIVIS values in practice, turning abstract aims such as societal impact and European citizenship into lived experiences of collaborative problem-solving.

7.3. Interdisciplinarity

A large majority of coordinators confirmed that their programmes fostered **interdisciplinary collaboration**, with **97.5% indicating that interdisciplinary approaches were encouraged** (Q21). Similarly, **97.5% reported that students from different disciplines were supported in working and learning together** (Q22).

The **examples provided by coordinators** (Q23) provide concrete examples illustrating how interdisciplinary collaboration was enacted within the programmes. These examples fall into three main areas: **interdisciplinary collaboration among students**, the **pedagogical strategies used by teachers to facilitate cross-disciplinary learning**, and the **ways in which students engaged through multicultural and multidisciplinary group dynamics**. Together, these insights offer a deeper understanding of how interdisciplinary principles were translated into practice within the learning environment.

Interdisciplinary collaboration among students

Across BIPs, coordinators consistently highlighted that **teachers intentionally structured learning environments to bring together students from different academic backgrounds and ensure meaningful interdisciplinary exchange**. In many cases, interdisciplinarity was embedded from the start: students were deliberately assigned to mixed teams composed of, for example, geographers, engineers, social scientists, computer scientists, linguists, and historians: *"One member was an environmental geographer (GIS mapping and terrain validation), another was an engineering MSc student focused on technical infrastructures on an environmental context and another was a remote sensing specialist."* *"The team structure of the project brought together students who studied linguistics with students from computer science and mathematics and history and archaeology."*

Teachers reinforced this diversity by designing tasks that required each discipline to contribute unique expertise, such as mapping environmental risks with GIS, analysing social or economic dimensions of climate change, or developing digital tools for linguistic analysis. This structure ensured that no group could solve the assigned tasks without integrating multiple disciplinary perspectives.

Pedagogical strategies used by teachers

Teachers also employed **specific pedagogical strategies to strengthen interdisciplinary learning**. Many programmes included collaborative workshops and problem-solving sessions where students had to combine their disciplinary lenses, such as developing **interdisciplinary impact chains**, designing **local sustainability interventions**, or working on **joint field-research projects**: *"Teaching sessions were delivered by lecturers and experts representing various disciplines, allowing students to approach the central topic from multiple academic and methodological angles."* *"Field research activities. Students worked in mixed thematic groups (4-5 members) to collect and analyse data on various environmental parameters. Each group focused on a different aspect (e.g., biodiversity, water chemistry, geomorphology), encouraging collaboration across disciplines."*

Several coordinators described *"skill exchange sessions"* where, for instance, linguistics students taught phonological principles while computer science students introduced coding for text analysis. In other cases, teachers used **co-teaching models**, bringing together experts from fields as diverse as biochemistry, neuroscience, cancer biology, architecture, sociology, economics, and law to model interdisciplinary dialogue for students.

Learning through multicultural and multidisciplinary group dynamics

Interdisciplinary work was further enhanced by the **multicultural composition of groups**, which helped students confront different epistemological traditions and forms of reasoning. Coordinators noted that discussions became richer when anthropology students challenged assumptions made by engineers, or art

history students introduced cultural and ethical perspectives that STEM students had not initially considered: *"This diversity greatly enriched the learning environment and allowed for the exploration of topics – such as ritual, sacrifice, and cultural heritage – from multiple, often unexpected angles."*

Teachers encouraged this exchange by assigning group tasks such as **destination rebranding**, **historical corpus annotation**, or **field-based climate change assessments**, in which students' disciplinary differences became assets rather than obstacles: *"Since place branding and attractiveness is an interdisciplinary subject itself, blending economics, political science, architecture, urban planning, management, marketing, etc., we managed to have a very heterogeneous crowd."*

In many programmes, the explicit goal was to **help students experience interdisciplinary as essential for solving complex societal challenges**, an outcome repeatedly confirmed in the coordinators' reflections.

Students reported a **very high level of encouragement to work and learn with colleagues from different areas of study**, indicating that the **programmes were strongly perceived as interdisciplinary and collaborative**, as **Figure 22** shows. Almost half of respondents stated that this occurred 'to a very great extent' (**49.10%**, **n=300**), and a further **35.84%** (**n=219**) answered 'to a great extent'. An additional 11.29% (n=69) considered this happened 'to some extent', while only a small minority indicated low levels of interdisciplinary interaction, with 2.78% (n=17) selecting 'to a small extent' and 0.98% (n=6) 'not at all'.

Figure 22. Extent to which BIPs encouraged working with and learning from colleagues from different areas of study

Statistically, this pattern is reflected in a **mean score of 4.293** on a 5-point scale, where 1 corresponds to 'not at all' and 5 to 'to a very great extent'. This average lies clearly in the upper range, between 'to a great extent' and 'to a very great extent', showing that, overall, **participants experienced the programme as strongly promoting cross-disciplinary collaboration and peer learning**. The standard deviation of 0.848 indicates relatively modest variability, with most responses clustered towards the top of the scale rather than being widely dispersed. The 95% confidence interval for the mean, from 4.226 to 4.360, together with a standard error of 0.034, demonstrates that this high estimate is statistically precise and robust.

Overall, these results suggest that the **programmes were highly successful in fostering opportunities for students from different academic backgrounds to work together, exchange perspectives, and learn from one another**, which is a key dimension of its interdisciplinary and international ambitions.

The open-ended examples illustrate concretely how the programmes encouraged participants to **work and learn with colleagues from different areas of study and backgrounds, and how it reflected CIVIS values in practice** (Q26). A central theme is **interdisciplinary group work**, where students from diverse fields

collaborated on shared tasks and projects. One participant, for example, described how in a group assignment *"each of us approached the task from a different angle [...] this mix of perspectives not only improved our final product but also helped me see how interdisciplinary dialogue can deepen understanding and creativity in research,"* highlighting how disciplinary diversity deepened the analysis and enriched the final output.

Another recurrent theme is **international and intercultural collaboration**: several respondents noted that *"we got to work in groups for our research project with people from different universities and backgrounds"* and that *"the programme provided a meaningful opportunity to work and learn alongside colleagues from diverse academic backgrounds [...] This interdisciplinary environment encouraged open dialogue and helped me appreciate how different areas of study contribute to solving complex problems,"* underlining the role of the programmes in broadening perspectives and fostering European and global citizenship.

Participants also pointed to **problem-based and project-based activities as concrete vehicles for interdisciplinary teamwork**. Group research tasks and intensive formats such as hackathons were frequently mentioned as powerful examples, with one student noting that *"I think the Hackathon that we had to prepare as a group project of 4 was the perfect example of interdisciplinary teamwork,"* where different academic profiles had to cooperate to design solutions to complex, real-world problems. Both online and in-person components contributed to this dynamic, as virtual collaboration tools and face-to-face sessions were used to coordinate tasks, exchange expertise, and build a sense of community.

Beyond illustrating interdisciplinary collaboration, the examples provided also highlight **several key facilitators of this learning model**. Participants pointed to **deliberately mixed-background groups and problem-based tasks as especially effective**. Working with students from other countries was repeatedly described as enriching, suggesting that the international, intercultural setting itself played a central role in broadening perspectives. At the same time, these hint at potential challenges, such as the **need to coordinate across diverse schedules and disciplinary backgrounds**, and to **ensure balanced participation within teams**. This indicates that while interdisciplinary, international group work is a major strength of the programmes, it also requires clear task design, structured guidance, and ongoing facilitation to fully realise its benefits for all students.

COMMUNICATION, OUTREACH AND FUTURE ENGAGEMENT

Figure 23 shows that information about the programmes circulated primarily through **university-based channels** rather than central CIVIS communication. Among 611 respondents, the most common source was teachers, mentioned by **42.23% (n=258)**, indicating that **academic staff play a pivotal role in promoting CIVIS activities**. The **CIVIS webpage was the second most frequent source at 23.90% (n=146)**, followed by **fellow students/colleagues at 16.04% (n=98)**, suggesting that peer networks are also an important vector for dissemination. Other central CIVIS channels contributed to a lesser extent: **CIVIS social media (Facebook, Instagram) accounted for 4.58% (n=29)**, **CIVIS events such as presentations or info days for 2.45% (n=15)**, and **CIVIS ambassadors for 2.13% (n=13)**. A further **8.67% (n=52)** selected 'Other', which likely captures a mix of institutional newsletters, departmental websites, or informal contacts.

Figure 23. Main source of information about the programmes

Substantively, the results highlight that **local mediation by teachers and peers is currently the dominant driver of awareness**, with central **CIVIS communication channels (webpage, social media, events, ambassadors) playing a secondary but still relevant role**. This suggests that strengthening collaboration with teaching staff and systematically equipping them with up-to-date CIVIS information, while also enhancing the visibility and reach of central channels, could further broaden and diversify student participation.

Responses indicate a **very strong willingness among participants to engage again with CIVIS activities in the future**. Out of 611 respondents, **84.29% (n=515)** answered 'Yes' to intending to enrol or attend other CIVIS experiences, while only **15.71% (n=96)** replied 'No.' The standard deviation of 0.364 is relatively low, indicating limited dispersion and suggesting that views are not strongly polarised but instead clustered towards a clear majority preference for continued participation. The standard error of 0.015 and the 95% confidence interval of 1.128 – 1.186 show that this estimate is statistically precise and robust.

Altogether, these findings suggest a **high level of overall satisfaction and perceived value of CIVIS programmes**, as most students are not only satisfied with their current experience but are also **motivated to seek further opportunities within the alliance**.

In their final comments, participants expressed a **predominantly positive view of their CIVIS experiences**, often emphasising how enriching they found the international and interdisciplinary dimension. Several students highlighted the **enthusiasm and commitment of staff**, noting that *"teachers know each other, are friends, and this enthusiasm was passed on to the students"* and describing the facilitators as **'amazing'**, with *"course content [that] is very relevant and interesting."* Many respondents linked their participation to a **stronger sense of European identity and belonging**, with one remarking that *"it has helped me to clearly understand*

what the European project is, something that in the past I had only heard of and felt a distant and abstract notion. This understanding is helping to create a sense of belonging and unity," and others simply stating that they were *"happy that [they] could take part in this opportunity."* These comments reinforce earlier findings that the **BIPs are perceived as intellectually stimulating, personally meaningful, and well organised.**

At the same time, students reiterated some structural and procedural challenges. Some pointed to **bureaucratic and recognition issues**, describing *"the process of validating the CIVIS course [as] extremely complicated by bureaucracy"* and calling for the ECTS credits earned *"to be formally recognized by [the] home university to support academic progression."* Others mentioned **logistical and workload-related concerns**, particularly around online components, explaining that *"the online part was sometimes difficult to combine with our schedule of work/school"* and indicating *"how lacking the online component was and how little it had to do, at times, with the in-person part of the course, which was very nurturing. I believe this course should undergo a major re-thinking because it holds a very valuable potential, as seen in the in-person part of it, but the two components are not properly combined to create a better learning experience."* A smaller number also asked for **more practical and hands-on activities to build further on the strong conceptual and collaborative foundations.** While many students clearly valued working on real-world problems, there are indications that the intensity and structure of these challenge-based components varied across programmes. Some participants implicitly contrasted this with more traditional courses that included only limited or peripheral challenge-based tasks. This variation suggests that, even though the average perception is strongly positive, the actual depth of integration of challenge-based learning is not fully uniform across the CIVIS portfolio.

Moreover, the open comments show that students are not only interested in the delivery of the programmes, but also in the **transparency and fairness of access to such opportunities.** Some students expressed a wish to understand better **why they were not selected for earlier CIVIS programmes or applications.** While this concern does not directly affect their overall rating of the course they eventually attended, it does point to an important expectation around clear selection criteria and feedback. Providing more explicit information on why applications are rejected, and how students can strengthen future applications, would help maintain trust and sustain the high level of interest in CIVIS experiences, especially among those who are motivated by the promise of authentic challenge-based work but have not yet been able to participate.

Overall, the responses paint a picture of students who are **highly appreciative of the academic quality, international context, and personal impact of CIVIS programmes,** while also clearly signalling the need for streamlined administrative procedures, more predictable recognition of credits, and further refinement of the digital and organisational setup to maximise the benefits of future editions.

9

BEST PRACTICES AND ADDED VALUE

9.1. Best practices

Coordinators identified a diverse set of best practices (Q26) that are both impactful and highly transferable across the CIVIS Alliance. Their examples reveal recurring patterns in how successful BIPs are designed and implemented, ranging from **interdisciplinary and international teamwork**, to **blended and phase-based learning structures**, to **strong digital ecosystems and value-driven pedagogical approaches**. The following synthesis illustrates these best practices in action, highlighting concrete cases that demonstrate how CIVIS educational activities can create meaningful, collaborative, and socially engaged learning experiences across multiple disciplines.

A recurring pattern is the **intentional use of mixed, international and interdisciplinary student groups working on real societal case studies**. For example, one programme systematically grouped students from different countries, disciplines and study levels to work on timely social challenges, guiding them step by step from problem framing, analysis, solution design, presentation and supporting them with formative feedback and a shared digital workspace. *"One of the strongest and most transferable elements of the programme was the use of international, mixed-discipline student groups working on real societal case studies, supported by structured guidance and formative feedback. This approach successfully combined intercultural exchange, interdisciplinary, and civic relevance, which aligns closely with CIVIS values and can be easily replicated in other BIPs or courses."*

In geomorphology-focused BIPs, mixed teams tackled **concrete environmental questions** such as landslide risk in the Swiss Alps or biogeographical corridors, bringing together GIS specialists, remote sensing experts, environmental geographers and students focused on socio-economic risk dimensions to co-produce richer, more integrated project outcomes. *"A key best practice that can be shared with a wider community is the use of a Blended Intensive Program (BIP) as a complementary tool to traditional university curricula."*

Another strong cluster of best practices relates to **blended, phase-based learning designs** that combine online preparation, intensive field or workshop components, and post-course mentoring. The Naxos summer school, for instance, uses a **three-phase structure** – preparatory online sessions, an intensive on-site summer school, and follow-up online workshops – to gradually build students' skills in computational historical linguistics, with clearly defined interdisciplinary roles (linguists, computer scientists, historians, mathematicians) and a flexible assessment portfolio including essays, computational projects, posters and exams. *"The following best practices should be distributed to the entire community: The three-phase structure of our program (preparatory online sessions followed by intensive summer school and online workshops) provided students with progressive learning opportunities that supported different skill levels while keeping academic standards high."*

In parallel, several coordinators pointed to **effective digital ecosystems as best practice**, most notably the combined use of Moodle as a central hub for materials, assignments and quizzes, and Zoom for synchronous, interactive sessions, which provided a simple but robust model for running international blended courses.

Finally, many best practices explicitly foreground **CIVIS values and innovative pedagogy**. In *AI and STEAM: Changing Learning, Shaping Futures*, for example, sessions on AI in education were designed as **transdisciplinary modules that bridged education, technology, art and business, with conceptual input, interactive activities and application-based assessments aligned to real educational and societal contexts** (*"[...] through a combination of conceptual lectures, interactive activities, and application-based assessments, students explored the role of AI across STEAM fields in real educational contexts"*). Other BIPs showcased *"mobile colloquia"* at significant sites such as the Roman Forum or religious heritage locations, where on-site teaching and discussion deepened students' understanding of European identity, rights and democracy.

Several coordinators also underlined the value of **opening courses to external stakeholders and NGOs**, whether in mountain research, urban sustainability or football and civic engagement, thus connecting academic learning with community needs and offering students networking and professional opportunities. Together, these examples illustrate a rich portfolio of practices – interdisciplinary teamwork, phased blended designs, strong digital support, and stakeholder-engaged learning – that can inspire future CIVIS BIPs across very different fields.

9.2. Added value

Coordinators' views on the added value of and distinctiveness of the CIVIS educational activity in contrast to educational activities outside of CIVIS (Q27) converge around three main themes: **enhanced transnational collaboration and intercultural exchange**; **strengthened interdisciplinary supported by cross-institutional teaching expertise**; and a **strong emphasis on civic engagement, societal impact, and European citizenship**. These dimensions collectively illustrate how CIVIS formats create learning opportunities that are broader, more collaborative, and more socially engaged than standard educational offerings.

Transnational collaboration and intercultural exchange. Coordinators repeatedly emphasised that bringing together students and teachers from multiple European universities, and often from non-European backgrounds, creates a **learning environment impossible to reproduce within a single institution**.

- International teamwork across universities leading to richer learning experiences: *"through its strong emphasis on international, interdisciplinary, and socially relevant learning," "genuinely transnational, interdisciplinary, and civic-oriented character."*
- Intercultural exchanges building tolerance, mutual understanding, and strong bonds among students and faculty: *"students create an international learning community which is in itself inductive to tolerance, understanding a culture of peace."*
- Exposure to teachers and students from many European universities and diverse cultures: *"the exposure to different teachers from different universities, and to students from European universities but coming from many other countries is paramount."*
- Mobility experiences transforming a physical location into a shared European classroom.
- Blended mobility allowing continuous collaboration before, during, and after the physical meeting: *"the combination of virtual and physical components allowed for flexible participation while maintaining the depth of experiential learning."*

Interdisciplinary and cross-institutional teaching expertise

- Joint teaching by experts from several universities, bringing together disciplines like AI, education, sustainability, law, economics, art, or geomorphology: *"the interdisciplinary and the opportunity to work together with (as a team and not only parallel to) other professors from renowned Universities-members of CIVIS."*
- Students from different fields working together, broadening their perspectives and critical thinking: *"the heterogeneity of the crowd (interdisciplinary) and opportunities offered by the mobility week are a distinctive trait of CIVIS that matters a lot for both students and professors."*
- Access to specialised expertise, computational tools, or resources that a single institution alone could not offer: *"the alliance enables member institutions can access specialised databases and computational resources and software licenses through shared resources which they could not obtain independently."*

Civic engagement, societal impact, and European citizenship

- Activities addressing real societal challenges, sustainability, democracy, citizenship, community engagement: *"collaboratively address real-world challenges at the intersection of technology, education, and society."*

- Students interacting with local stakeholders, municipalities, NGOs, or community groups: *"[...] CIVIS activity integrated stakeholder engagement directly into the curriculum. Students interacted with local authorities, environmental agencies, and industry representatives."*
- Strengthening European citizenship and a sense of belonging to a shared European space: *"[...] lies in its strong message of belonging to a shared European academic and civic space."*

10

CHALLENGES AND AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT

10.1. Challenges

The analysis of responses reveals a diverse but clearly patterned set of **challenges encountered across the different phases of CIVIS BIP implementation** (Q28). These challenges extend beyond isolated difficulties and point to recurring structural, procedural, and contextual issues that shape how BIPs are planned, delivered, and sustained. To provide clarity and analytical coherence, the results are organised into four main categories: **administrative, academic and pedagogical, communication, and other cross-cutting challenges**, reflecting both the frequency of responses and the nature of the issues reported. This categorisation helps highlight where obstacles are most concentrated and where targeted institutional or alliance-level interventions may have the greatest impact.

Administrative challenges

Administrative challenges are the most frequently reported and cut across all phases of the BIP lifecycle: application, validation, implementation, and reporting. Respondents consistently describe processes as **overly bureaucratic, time-consuming, and insufficiently coordinated across partner universities**. The volume of paperwork, repeated data requests, rigid timelines, and delays in payments or approvals place a significant burden on academic staff, often requiring them to “discover” procedures as the programme unfolds. As one respondent succinctly noted that *“the administrative process is unduly cumbersome,”* while another simply stated *“too much administration”* and *“a lot of paperwork.”*

Delays related to validation, funding, and post-implementation reporting were particularly problematic. Several respondents highlighted late payments caused by incomplete registrations from partner institutions, which in turn delayed reimbursements and strained local budgets: *“In many occasions, the total funding is late... This results very often in us delaying to pay expenses.”* Others pointed to redundant reporting requirements: *“You want the BIP coordinator to provide again data... such info has already been given to the CIVIS office.”* Overall, these administrative burdens risk undermining sustainability and staff motivation, especially when the teaching effort is not formally recognised within institutional workload models.

Academic and pedagogical challenges

Academic and pedagogical challenges mainly relate to **student engagement, group dynamics, interdisciplinarity, and alignment across diverse academic cultures**. Several respondents reported uneven levels of student commitment and participation, particularly in online or hybrid components: *“Not all students approached the academic work with the same level of seriousness,”* and *“maintaining high levels of student engagement in virtual settings was sometimes difficult.”* These issues affected discussion quality, group work, and the overall learning environment.

Additional pedagogical complexity arose from **interdisciplinarity and long programme durations**. Coordinators noted the need for sustained facilitation and follow-up to maintain coherence over several months: *“Because this course spans through several months, a person is needed to assure smooth connections... continuous reminders.”* Differences in assessment practices, grading systems, and expectations across universities also posed challenges: *“The assessment and the notes are very different in each University.”* Together, these factors require additional pedagogical coordination and support structures that are not always formally provided.

Communication challenges

Communication challenges relate both to **internal coordination** and to **information flow between CIVIS structures, institutional offices, and academic coordinators**. Several respondents reported insufficient clarity

regarding application procedures, deadlines, and responsibilities, especially when timelines changed. One coordinator described missing a call entirely due to miscommunication: *"You changed the deadline... the office in our university did not inform us correctly and neither CIVIS."* Another noted that *"It is difficult to find out about the application process,"* particularly when deadlines were brought forward significantly.

There were also challenges in **reaching the right contact persons and obtaining an overview of responsibilities**: *"Fluidity to reach each task/module manager... an overview would have been nice."* While communication support during application phases was sometimes praised, respondents expressed a need for continued support during implementation and reporting, including help with documentation and dissemination of results.

Other challenges (financial, structural, and contextual)

Some challenges point to broader structural and contextual issues. **Funding constraints** were repeatedly mentioned, particularly in relation to student mobility, cost of living differences, and inclusion. One respondent observed that *"Student mobility is severely underfunded... this disadvantages students in southern Europe,"* while another highlighted that accommodation costs discouraged participation despite standard grants. Funding gaps also affected staffing and programme quality: *"The programme faced difficulties in obtaining sufficient funding for teaching assistants and visiting professors."*

Equity and inclusion issues also emerged, especially regarding **visa procedures and participation of African partners**: *"Integrating African students in CIVIS activities (administrative hurdles),"* and *"Visa issues for African students."* Finally, **limited curricular integration and recognition** further reduced impact: *"The absence of a clear framework for embedding BIPs into degree programmes reduced academic visibility and student motivation."* These challenges suggest that beyond procedural improvements, systemic adjustments are needed to ensure accessibility, equity, and long-term viability of CIVIS BIPs.

10.2. Improvements

Coordinators highlight a range of **improvements implemented or proposed to enhance the quality, effectiveness, and sustainability of the educational activities**. These improvements reflect both responsive adjustments made during implementation and forward-looking suggestions informed by participant and staff feedback. For analytical clarity, the results are organised into three main categories: **academic and pedagogical improvements**, **communication and coordination enhancements**, and **structural or resource-related measures**, illustrating how targeted changes at different levels can collectively strengthen the overall CIVIS BIP experience.

Academic and pedagogical improvements

Many respondents highlighted improvements aimed at **strengthening learning quality, student engagement, and inclusiveness across diverse academic backgrounds**. A recurring theme is better scaffolding and preparation, particularly through extended preparatory phases, clearer assignments, and alignment of activities with transdisciplinary learners' needs. Sharing key readings in advance, extending online preparation periods, and adapting tasks in real time helped reduce disparities in prior knowledge and enabled deeper engagement: *"Participants were better prepared in advance through the sharing of key readings and reference frameworks, which helped them engage more deeply with the course content."*

Improvements also focused on **active and practice-based learning**, including clearer group roles, additional formative feedback, and the integration of fieldwork or laboratory activities. These adjustments addressed uneven participation and enhanced hands-on learning: *"Clearer roles (moderator, note-taker, presenter) were assigned within groups,"* and *"we could add some wet lab activities in our programme (requested by the students)."* Several responses point to an iterative, reflective approach, where student feedback directly informed

pedagogical refinements: *"We are adapting our planning based on students' comments from last year. This is a learning process."*

Communication and coordination improvements

Improved communication emerged as a key aspect for enhancing both student experience and institutional coordination. Respondents stressed the value of **earlier planning**, **clearer timelines**, and **structured pre-course communication**, which supported engagement and reduced uncertainty: *"Earlier planning and clearer coordination between partner institutions would improve the process. More structured pre-course communication could support student engagement."*

At the course level, **clearer communication channels and digital support tools** improved collaboration and participation, especially in distributed or hybrid settings. Examples include tutorials for online platforms, standardised communication procedures, and additional synchronous and asynchronous touchpoints: *"Additional support was provided for using shared online platforms, including step-by-step guidance and short tutorials,"* and *"the introduction of clearer communication channels for group coordination... contributed to smoother course delivery."* Some programmes also reported that **standardised communication between partners** reduced delays in grading and certification, demonstrating that communication improvements can have direct administrative and academic benefits.

Structural, recognition, and resource-related improvements

Beyond pedagogy and communication, a third set of improvements relates to **structural support, recognition, and resources**, which directly affect sustainability. Several respondents emphasised the need for **official curricular validation and academic recognition of BIPs** to motivate staff and students: *"Establishing academic recognition mechanisms would enhance staff involvement,"* and *"Official validation in the curriculum."*

Funding and staffing support were also identified as critical areas for improvement. Increased budgets, mobility grants, and access to teaching or research assistants were seen as necessary to maintain quality and inclusiveness: *"It is important that CIVIS can offer personnel, research and teaching assistants and grants,"* and *"increasing the budget related to the students' participation limits."* While not strictly pedagogical, these improvements enable better supervision, richer learning activities, and equitable participation, reinforcing the academic and communicative dimensions of CIVIS BIPs.

Overall, the identified improvements suggest that while many BIPs are already perceived as successful, their impact can be strengthened through enhanced pedagogical scaffolding, clearer and earlier communication, and stronger institutional and resource support. Together, these areas form a coherent improvement framework grounded in practical experience and participant feedback.

11

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMENDATIONS

A consolidated set of conclusions and recommendations derive from the analysis of the main results presented in this report, namely **administrative aspects, mobility, teaching and learning, digital platforms, CIVIS values, best practices, and identified challenges and areas for improvement**. Drawing on both quantitative and qualitative evidence from students' and coordinators' feedback, the conclusions synthesise the key strengths of CIVIS BIPs alongside the structural and operational constraints that continue to shape their implementation. The recommendations aim to provide actionable guidance for strengthening institutional processes, enhancing the quality and inclusiveness of learning and mobility experiences, and supporting the continued development and sustainability of CIVIS BIPs within the broader framework of European university cooperation.

Administrative aspects

The administrative framework supporting CIVIS BIPs is generally robust and effective. Both students and coordinators report high levels of satisfaction with the organisation, scheduling, and digital handling of administrative procedures. **Administrative support emerges as the strongest pillar of the CIVIS ecosystem**, playing a critical role in enabling participation and compensating for procedural complexity. Nevertheless, recurring challenges persist, particularly regarding the volume of documentation required, the complexity of Learning Agreement procedures, and inconsistencies in ECTS recognition across institutions. Recommendations:

- Simplify and further harmonise administrative procedures across CIVIS universities, particularly for Learning Agreements and documentation workflows.
- Strengthen early and transparent communication on ECTS recognition conditions at home institutions.
- Reduce administrative burden on academic coordinators by reinforcing dedicated support roles at institutional level.

Mobility experience

The mobility component of CIVIS BIPs is widely perceived as well organised and positively supported. Students report high satisfaction with the overall mobility process, course locations, and accessibility. However, financial aspects, especially the timing and adequacy of payments, remain a recurrent source of concern. Green mobility uptake remains limited, not due to lack of motivation, but because of structural constraints related to time, cost, geography, and administrative procedures. Recommendations:

- Improve predictability and transparency regarding mobility funding timelines and payment procedures.
- Provide clearer guidance and earlier information on green travel options, eligibility, and reimbursement procedures.
- Explore complementary institutional or CIVIS-level measures to support green mobility where Erasmus+ constraints limit feasibility.

Teaching and learning

Teaching and learning quality constitutes one of the strongest dimensions of CIVIS BIPs. Students report very high satisfaction with both the quality and relevance of learning activities, particularly those that are experiential, applied, and interactive. There is strong alignment between announced programme design and actual delivery, reinforcing trust and credibility. Active learning, group work, fieldwork, and hands-on activities are central to student engagement and perceived relevance. Recommendations:

- Continue prioritising experiential, practice-based, and collaborative learning formats across BIPs.
- Support coordinators in balancing ambitious pedagogical designs with realistic timeframes and resource constraints.
- Encourage systematic reflection on student workload and prior knowledge to ensure inclusive participation.

Digital platforms and learning environment

Digital platforms play a stabilising and enabling role in CIVIS BIPs, particularly for blended and online components. Moodle and institutional digital tools are generally perceived as reliable and supportive. However, the CIVIS mobility platform is frequently described as complex and time-consuming, especially for coordinators managing student status and post-mobility processes. Recommendations:

- Improve the usability and efficiency of the CIVIS digital campus, with particular attention to coordinator workflows.
- Provide targeted training and user guidance for both students and staff on digital tools.
- Ensure stronger alignment between digital platforms and administrative processes to reduce duplication and errors.

CIVIS values and interdisciplinarity

CIVIS values such as interdisciplinarity, international collaboration, civic engagement, and challenge-based learning are strongly reflected in the design and delivery of BIPs. Students and coordinators value the opportunity to work in diverse, international teams and to engage with real-world challenges. However, institutional structures do not always fully support the curricular integration of these innovative formats. Recommendations:

- Strengthen institutional recognition of interdisciplinary and challenge-based learning within formal curricula.
- Promote shared CIVIS guidelines on embedding BIPs and recognising interdisciplinary learning outcomes.
- Enhance communication of CIVIS values at institutional level to foster broader ownership and alignment.

Best practices

Best practices across CIVIS BIPs include **strong administrative support, high-quality teaching, experiential learning, effective collaboration among partner universities**, and **consistent alignment between programme design and delivery**. The added value of BIPs is evident at student, academic, and institutional levels, particularly in terms of international exposure, skills development, and network building. Recommendations:

- Systematically document and disseminate best practices across the CIVIS Alliance.
- Encourage peer learning among coordinators through communities of practice and targeted workshops.
- Use best practices as reference models for future BIP calls and programme development.

Challenges and areas for improvement

Key challenges identified across chapters include **administrative complexity, uneven ECTS recognition, time constraints, limited pedagogical support structures**, and the **operationalisation of green mobility**. These challenges are largely systemic rather than programme-specific and reflect broader institutional and regulatory contexts. Recommendations:

- Address challenges through coordinated CIVIS-level actions rather than isolated institutional solutions.
- Invest in structured pedagogical support and instructional design guidance for coordinators.
- Strengthen post-programme follow-up mechanisms, particularly for recognition, reimbursement,

Overall, **CIVIS BIPs demonstrate a high level of maturity, quality, and added value**. The combination of strong administrative foundations, innovative teaching practices, and commitment to CIVIS values positions BIPs as a flagship instrument of European university cooperation. Addressing remaining structural and procedural challenges will further enhance their sustainability, inclusiveness, and impact.

ANNEXES

Annex I. Programme coordinators survey 2025

INTRODUCTION MESSAGE

Dear BIP and Micro-Programme Coordinators,

Thank you for your commitment and involvement in the design, coordination, and implementation of CIVIS educational activities.

As part of our ongoing efforts to improve the quality and impact of **Blended Intensive Programmes (BIPs)** and **Micro-Programmes** across the CIVIS Alliance, we kindly ask for your input by completing this survey.

We are committed to protecting your personal data in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Before you begin this survey, please read the following information.

Your feedback is essential to help us better understand the experiences, challenges, and successes related to the coordination of these programs. The information you provide will contribute to improving institutional processes, enhancing student and staff experiences, and fostering innovation and collaboration within CIVIS.

The survey is structured into thematic sections covering academic contributions, participation, support received, accreditation, teaching and learning practices, pedagogical innovation, digital tools, and best practices. Participation is entirely voluntary. You may stop at any time without any consequences. Your responses are anonymous and will only be used for research purposes.

We estimate that it will take approximately **20-30 minutes** to complete. Please respond as thoroughly and accurately as possible.

By continuing with this survey, you confirm that you have read and understood this information and consent to your data being used as described above.

We sincerely appreciate your time and valuable insights.

SECTION I: ACADEMIC TEAM

Home University (*pick from list*):

- Aix-Marseille Université (France)
- Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen (Germany)
- National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (Greece)
- Sapienza Università di Roma (Italia)
- Stockholm University (Sweden)
- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Spain)
- Université Libre de Bruxelles (Belgium)
- University of Bucharest (Romania)
- University of Glasgow (UK)
- University of Salzburg (Austria)
- Université de Lausanne (Switzerland)
- Université Hassan II de Casablanca (Morocco)
- Université Cheikh Anta Diop de Dakar (Senegal)
- Eduardo Mondlane University (Mozambique)
- Université de Sfax (Tunisia)
- University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)
- Makerere University (Uganda)

Type of programme

- Blended Intensive Programme (BIP)
- Micro-programme

Name of educational activity attended (*drop-down list*):

- À l'école des Anciens. War and its representations from the perspective of ancient rhetoric;
- A revival of ideologies? Ideas and opinions in contemporary democracies
- AI and STEAM: Changing Learning, Shaping Futures
- Anatomy of Trauma and its Implications for Addictions
- Animal sacrifice and its critics between past and present
- Attractiveness, branding and governance of regions
- Basic Cell Biology
- Basis and Methods of Localisation Translation of Computer Products and Video Games
- Biological Basis of Aging and Related Diseases
- Brulau: Ecole doctorale francophone en études de genre
- Civic Engagement & Football: A Transdisciplinary Approach
- CIVIS Engagement (MP)
- Climate change and landscape evolution in the Mediterranean context
- Climate change imprint on a tectonically active landscape
- Co-Creating Urban Futures
- Communicating Social Science and Humanities: Mastering Methodological Challenges and Early Publishing
- Delve into Santorini's geological marvels and volcanic risks
- Democracy, Citizens; New Forms of Civic Engagement
- Diachronic Linguistics in the 21st century
- Digital Transformations in Health and Wellbeing (MP)
- Environmental challenges facing Danube River Basin
- Equitable and Just Digital Society (MP)
- EU Decision making and its institutions: discover the heart of Brussels
- Euro-African Trade and Investment Relations and the Polycrisis
- Europe and the Rule of Law
- European Election in times of (poli)crises.
- European Renaissance IV: Western versus Eastern Europe
- Experimental Models in Molecular Biomedicine (EMMB)
- Exploring Language Varieties in the Diaspora: Methodological and Theoretical Approaches
- Global Awareness (MP)
- H2O Pollution: holistic approach and nature-based solutions
- How to write a paper and talk about science
- Humanities within Medicine and Health
- Immuno-oncology in the spatial omics era
- Interplay of Landscape, Tectonics and Climate Change in the Mediterranean context
- Law, Community and Justice
- Let's prove it! Reasoning in different contexts
- Linguistic cultures and communities in Europe (past and present). Building the EUROTALLES museum.
- Maternal and neonatal vaccination
- Medical Matters in Post/colonial Situations/ Matérielités médicales en situations post/coloniales
- Mental Health, Sport & Physical Activity (MHSPA)
- Molecular Scale Biophysics
- Multicultural and multilingual Mediation (German language)
- Natural products: applications, formulations
- Navigating Uncertainty: Building Sustainable Skills for Life
- Neurobiology of Mental Disorders
- New insight in Drug design and discovery: from the bench to the patient
- Non-coding RNAs in Health and Disease
- Novel Research and Ethics: from Neuroscience to AI
- Online fake news and disinformation: recognize and verify
- Participatory tools for urban nature planning and management
- Pluralism of economic ideas

- PostRacial Transmodernities: Afro-European Relations, Mediterranean Trajectories & Intercultural Reciprocities
- Quantifying vulnerability to natural hazards in changing climate patterns. New perspectives and methods
- Radiotheranostics in Nuclear Medicine
- Rare Diseases at the Omics era: Current tools for frequent challenges
- Reading Between the Humorous Lines
- Refugees, Migrants, and Exiles in German and Comparative Literature
- Religion and power in the Eastern Mediterranean
- Rights and Democracy. The Multilevel Protection of Fundamental Rights and the Role of Constitutional and European Courts
- Roman Mobilities and their Afterlives
- Rome CIVIS Orchestra Academy 2025
- Science, Ethics & Governance of Human Genome Editing
- Scientific Communication and Linguistic Corpora: Tools for Interdisciplinary Research
- Social Sciences Going Public - Research and Practice with, in and for the Society
- Strategic Communication for Social Change
- Surgical Anatomy- from theory to dissection
- Teaching and Studying Turkish Politics through Literature (second edition, 2025)
- The challenge of sustainability in European democracies
- The Ethics of narratives: between old and new media
- The Heritage of Money and Coinage: objects and practices in transformation
- TRANSMOUNT - Transitions in Mountain Environments
- Understanding Earth
- Using Drones in Environmental Sciences

Please fill in with the dates of all academics involved in delivering the educational activity.

Upload a file

Please download the template, fill it and upload it above:
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1yKJPSm9a-sMkp8lkzA1DbAl6Up9KclOrcrYUgWD4Nrc/edit?usp=sharing>

SECTION II: PARTICIPATION OF STUDENTS

Rate of drop-out

Students enrolled, but no show-up (the students were admitted, confirmation were sent, but the students never replied/participated)	<i>Insert number</i>
Participated, but did not pass (the student participated in some of the activities, but did not pass, either due to fail or due to drop out)	<i>Insert number</i>
Passed	<i>Insert number</i>

SECTION III: TYPE OF SUPPORT RECEIVED

Type of support	Received (Yes/No)	Shortly describe the received support	Body/entity at your university or in CIVIS	Level of satisfaction (<i>very dissatisfied / rather dissatisfied / rather satisfied / very satisfied</i>)
Financial support	Yes/No	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>	Select from scale
Administrative	Yes/No	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>	Select from scale

support				
Technical	Yes/No	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>	Select from scale
Dissemination	Yes/No	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>	Select from scale
Pedagogical	Yes/No	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>	Select from scale
Other	Yes/No	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>	Select from scale

Comments

Insert text here...

SECTION IV: ACCREDITATION ISSUES

Was your BIP/micro-programme embedded in your university's curriculum?

- Yes
- No

If No, can you please describe why?

Insert text here...

How do you perceive the validation process for CIVIS BIPs/micro-programs in your university?

- Very difficult
- Difficult
- Easy
- Very easy

Please briefly describe how this process looks like.

Insert text here...

What challenges are in place when validating / accrediting / embedding CIVIS BIPs in your university?

Insert text here...

SECTION V: TEACHING AND LEARNING ACTIVITIES

Planned teaching and learning activities Please mention between 3-5 activities that you find more relevant.

Activity	Shortly describe the activity	Implemented (Yes/No)	Reasons for not implementing
Activity 1	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>	<i>Insert text</i>
Activity 2	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>	<i>Insert text</i>
Activity 3	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>	<i>Insert text</i>
Activity 4	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>	<i>Insert text</i>
Activity 5	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>	<i>Insert text</i>

Active participation. Please describe 1-4 teaching and learning activities in which participants were actively involved and reflect for each of them upon: How were the participants involved, limitations of the activity, reluctance from participants, ways to improve participation etc.

Insert text here...

Format and methods of assessment. Those who can report the information below through the university's study documentation IT-system can upload this document instead. Please mention between 3-5 methods that you find more relevant.

Method	Methods of assessment used	Reflections
Method 1	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>
Method 2	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>
Method 3	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>
Method 4	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>
Method 5	<i>Insert text</i>	<i>Insert text</i>

Have the participants reached the learning outcomes?

- Yes
- No

If Yes, how did you support them in reaching the learning outcomes? / If No, what were the obstacles in reaching the learning outcomes?

Insert text here...

Where the learning outcomes related to the teaching and learning activities and the assessment?

- Yes
- No

If yes, how where they related? (give 1-2 examples)

Insert text here...

SECTION VI: INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGIES

CIVIS Values: Did your programme's pedagogical design reflect the CIVIS values of civic engagement, societal impact, and European citizenship?

- Yes
- No

If yes, can you share specific examples of how this was integrated into learning activities or assessments?

Insert text here...

Interdisciplinary: Did you encourage students from different disciplines to work together and learn from each other?

- Yes
- No

If yes, please share specific examples

Insert text here...

SECTION VII: CIVIS DIGITAL CAMPUS

Did you leverage the CIVIS Digital Campus or other shared digital resources to support? (ex. Mobility Platform, Moodle)?

- Yes
- No

What features or functionalities were most valuable for your BIP? Could you give an example? What features or functionalities are missing but would be useful? What could be improved?

Insert text here...

SECTION VIII: BEST PRACTICES AND ADDED VALUE

In case of best practices that can be shared to a wider community (CIVIS or outside of the Alliance), please share here your example.

Insert text here...

Please specify the added value and distinctiveness (if applicable) of the CIVIS educational activity in contrast to educational activities outside of CIVIS.

Insert text here...

SECTION IX: CHALLENGES AND IMPROVEMENTS

Please mention (if applicable) 1-3 challenges that you encountered during all the phases of the educational activity (application, planning, implementation, reporting etc.)

Insert text here...

Please mention (if applicable) improvements of the educational activity implemented.

Insert text here...

Annex II. Student survey 2025

INTRODUCTION MESSAGE

Dear students,

Whether this was your first CIVIS activity or one of many, your feedback will help us refine our programmes and better support future participants.

We are committed to protecting your personal data in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Before you begin this survey, please read the following information.

This survey is designed for students who have taken part in **CIVIS Blended Intensive Programs (BIPs)** or **Micro-Programmes**. It covers various aspects of your experience: *academic, administrative, mobility-related, and educational*. Participation is entirely voluntary. You may stop at any time without any consequences. Your responses are anonymous and will only be used for research purposes.

The survey takes approximately **10-15 minutes** to complete.

By continuing with this survey, you confirm that you have read and understood this information and consent to your data being used as described above.

Thank you for contributing to the improvement of CIVIS learning experiences!

SECTION I: ACADEMIC INFORMATION

Home University (*pick from list*):

- Aix-Marseille Université (France)
- Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen (Germany)
- National and Kapodistrian University of Athens (Greece)
- Sapienza Università di Roma (Italia)
- Stockholm University (Sweden)
- Universidad Autónoma de Madrid (Spain)
- Université Libre de Bruxelles (Belgium)
- University of Bucharest (Romania)
- University of Glasgow (UK)
- University of Salzburg (Austria)
- Université de Lausanne (Switzerland)
- Université Hassan II de Casablanca (Morocco)
- Université Cheikh Anta Diop de Dakar (Senegal)
- Eduardo Mondlane University (Mozambique)
- Université de Sfax (Tunisia)
- University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa)
- Makerere University (Uganda)

Education level

- Bachelor
- Master
- Doctoral

Is this your first CIVIS experience

- Yes
- No

If No, please mention what other CIVIS experiences you took part of:

Insert text here...

Type of programme

- Blended Intensive Programme (BIP)
- Micro-programme

Name of educational activity attended *(drop-down list)*:

- À l'école des Anciens. War and its representations from the perspective of ancient rhetoric;
- A revival of ideologies? Ideas and opinions in contemporary democracies
- AI and STEAM: Changing Learning, Shaping Futures
- Anatomy of Trauma and its Implications for Addictions
- Animal sacrifice and its critics between past and present
- Attractiveness, branding and governance of regions
- Basic Cell Biology
- Basis and Methods of Localisation Translation of Computer Products and Video Games
- Biological Basis of Aging and Related Diseases
- Brulau: Ecole doctorale francophone en études de genre
- Civic Engagement & Football: A Transdisciplinary Approach
- CIVIS Engagement (MP)
- Climate change and landscape evolution in the Mediterranean context
- Climate change imprint on a tectonically active landscape
- Co-Creating Urban Futures
- Communicating Social Science and Humanities: Mastering Methodological Challenges and Early Publishing
- Delve into Santorini's geological marvels and volcanic risks
- Democracy, Citizens; New Forms of Civic Engagement
- Diachronic Linguistics in the 21st century
- Digital Transformations in Health and Wellbeing (MP)
- Environmental challenges facing Danube River Basin
- Equitable and Just Digital Society (MP)
- EU Decision making and its institutions: discover the heart of Brussels
- Euro-African Trade and Investment Relations and the Polycrisis
- Europe and the Rule of Law
- European Election in times of (poli)crises.
- European Renaissance IV: Western versus Eastern Europe
- Experimental Models in Molecular Biomedicine (EMMB)
- Exploring Language Varieties in the Diaspora: Methodological and Theoretical Approaches
- Global Awareness (MP)
- H2O Pollution: holistic approach and nature-based solutions
- How to write a paper and talk about science
- Humanities within Medicine and Health
- Immuno-oncology in the spatial omics era
- Interplay of Landscape, Tectonics and Climate Change in the Mediterranean context
- Law, Community and Justice
- Let's prove it! Reasoning in different contexts
- Linguistic cultures and communities in Europe (past and present). Building the EUROTALLES museum.
- Maternal and neonatal vaccination
- Medical Matters in Post/colonial Situations/ Matérialités médicales en situations post/coloniales
- Mental Health, Sport & Physical Activity (MHSPA)
- Molecular Scale Biophysics
- Multicultural and multilingual Mediation (German language)
- Natural products: applications, formulations
- Navigating Uncertainty: Building Sustainable Skills for Life
- Neurobiology of Mental Disorders
- New insight in Drug design and discovery: from the bench to the patient
- Non-coding RNAs in Health and Disease
- Novel Research and Ethics: from Neuroscience to AI

- Online fake news and disinformation: recognize and verify
- Participatory tools for urban nature planning and management
- Pluralism of economic ideas
- PostRacial Transmodernities: Afro-European Relations, Mediterranean Trajectories & Intercultural Reciprocities
- Quantifying vulnerability to natural hazards in changing climate patterns. New perspectives and methods
- Radiotheranostics in Nuclear Medicine
- Rare Diseases at the Omics era: Current tools for frequent challenges
- Reading Between the Humorous Lines
- Refugees, Migrants, and Exiles in German and Comparative Literature
- Religion and power in the Eastern Mediterranean
- Rights and Democracy. The Multilevel Protection of Fundamental Rights and the Role of Constitutional and European Courts
- Roman Mobilities and their Afterlives
- Rome CIVIS Orchestra Academy 2025
- Science, Ethics & Governance of Human Genome Editing
- Scientific Communication and Linguistic Corpora: Tools for Interdisciplinary Research
- Social Sciences Going Public - Research and Practice with, in and for the Society
- Strategic Communication for Social Change
- Surgical Anatomy- from theory to dissection
- Teaching and Studying Turkish Politics through Literature (second edition, 2025)
- The challenge of sustainability in European democracies
- The Ethics of narratives: between old and new media
- The Heritage of Money and Coinage: objects and practices in transformation
- TRANSMOUNT - Transitions in Mountain Environments
- Understanding Earth
- Using Drones in Environmental Sciences

SECTION II: ADMINISTRATIVE ISSUES

How did you perceive the application process?

- Very difficult
- Difficult
- Easy
- Very easy

What were the main challenges you encountered when you applied for the programme *(choose the two main challenges from your point of view)?*

- Lack of information on the application process
- Too much information and documents needed
- Too little time for the application
- Getting the relevant documents from the administrative staff
- Getting the signature on the Learning Agreement
- Recognition of ECTS from BIP
- No challenge
- Other _____

What were the areas in which you received the most support *(CIVIS, own university)?*

- Administrative support
- Academic support
- Support from student initiatives
- Help with personal needs and problems

- Mental health support
- Help with inclusion needs
- Other _____

How satisfied were you with the following aspects?

	Very dissatisfied	Rather dissatisfied	Rather satisfied	Very satisfied
Schedule	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Organisation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Digital platforms used	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

How satisfied were you with the level support received before, during and after the implementation of the program (CIVIS, own university)?

	Very dissatisfied	Rather dissatisfied	Rather satisfied	Very satisfied
Before the programme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
During the programme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
After the programme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

SECTION III: MOBILITY (APPLICABLE TO ACTIVITIES WITH PHYSICAL MOBILITY)

How would you rate the overall process of organizing and completing your (Erasmus) mobility (including information received, support, and administrative steps)?

- Very poor
- Poor
- Good
- Very good
- Not the case

What were the main challenges regarding the mobility?

- Information received about the process
- Amount of money received
- When was the money received
- Other _____

Did you use green travel?

- Yes
- No

If Yes, would you do it again and why? / If No, why, what were the hurdles (time, money, not being aware) Please name concrete incentives that would you make changing your mind and consider traveling green next time.

Insert text here..

How satisfied were you with the following aspects of the physical mobility?

	Very dissatisfied	Rather dissatisfied	Rather satisfied	Very satisfied
Accommodation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Catering	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Location of the courses	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The accessibility of the location	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

SECTION IV: LEARNING EXPERIENCE

How satisfied were you with the quality of learning and teaching activities that you took part of in the program you attended?

- Very dissatisfied
- Not satisfied
- Rather satisfied
- Very satisfied

Please mention between 2-3 learning activities that you found more relevant.

Insert text here...

What were the main aspects that you most enjoyed about the program you attended (*name max. 3 that are more relevant for you*)?

- Content
- Teaching practices/methods
- Communication and collaboration with teachers
- Communication and collaboration with fellow students
- Learning outcomes
- Other _____

How appropriate were the assessment methods used in this course (e.g., tests, projects, presentations) for evaluating what you learned?

- Very inappropriate
- Rather Inappropriate
- Rather Appropriate
- Very appropriate

**What worked well, and what could be improved in the way your learning was assessed?
Comments/Suggestions:**

Insert text here...

To what extent did the actual educational activity match what was presented or announced beforehand (e.g. in terms of content, format, or organisation)?

- Not at all similar
- Slightly similar
- Somewhat similar
- Very similar
- Exactly as presented

To what extent you believe that the programme you attended reflected the CIVIS values of civic engagement, societal impact, and European citizenship?

- Not at all
- To a small extent
- To some extent
- To a great extent
- To a very great extent

To what extent do you believe that the programme you attended encouraged you to work and learn from colleagues from different areas of study?

- Not at all
- To a small extent
- To some extent
- To a great extent
- To a very great extent

If the case, please share a specific example.

Insert text here...

To what extent do you believe that the program you attended included any elements of challenge-based learning, where students tackle real-world problems related to the CIVIS focus areas (e.g., health, climate, cities)?

- Not at all
- To a small extent
- To some extent
- To a great extent
- To a very great extent

If the case, how did this impact your engagement and learning outcomes?

Insert text here...

How satisfied were you with the following?

	Very dissatisfied	Rather dissatisfied	Rather satisfied	Very satisfied
Digital platform(s) for sharing resource	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Platform(s) for synchronous activities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

What features or functionalities are missing but would be useful? What could be improved?

Insert text here...

SECTION V: LEARNING EXPERIENCE

Were you able to recognise your ECTS?

- Yes
- No

If Yes, how did your university recognise the ECTS from the programme you attended?

- Embedded in the degree (part of regular ECTS)
- Extra ECTS in the diploma supplement
- Other _____

If No, please explain what happened.

Insert text here...

How did you find out about the programme?

- CIVIS webpage
- CIVIS social media (Facebook, Instagram)
- Teachers
- Fellow students Colleagues
- CIVIS ambassadors
- CIVIS events (presentations, workshops, info days)
- Other _____

Do you intend to enrol attend in other CIVIS experiences?

- Yes
- No

If there is anything that you want to add that you feel is relevant, please let us know.

Insert text here...